

THE ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE USSR
INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL PHYSICS

E. S. Medvedev

DETERMINATION OF A NEW MOLECULAR CONSTANT FOR
DIATOMIC SYSTEMS. NORMAL INTENSITY DISTRIBUTION LAW
FOR OVERTONE SPECTRA OF DIATOMIC AND POLYATOMIC
MOLECULES AND ANOMALIES IN OVERTONE ABSORPTION
SPECTRA OF DIATOMIC MOLECULES

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An analytical expression for the dipole moment matrix elements is derived using the quasiclassical approximation. Its exponential part depends on the potential function $\mathcal{E}(q)$ alone, the dipole moment function $d(q)$ entering only the preexponential factor, which is a slow function of the energy difference between the initial and final states. Higher overtone band intensities are shown to be governed by the repulsive portion of $\mathcal{E}(q)$ at large negative displacements q from the equilibrium position where $\mathcal{E}(q)$ greatly exceeds the dissociation energy. An intensity distribution law for overtone spectra called here as normal is derived from the exponential part of the dipole moment matrix element assuming $\mathcal{E}(q)$ to be proportional to $\exp(-2\beta q)$ at $q \ll 0$. The normal law is represented by a straight line on the plot of the logarithmic intensity vs. the square root of the energy of the upper level. The slope of the straight line is expressed in terms of the fundamental and well-known molecular constants as well as the parameter β , which is commonly used to describe the repulsive potentials in atomic collisions involving rare gas atoms and which is introduced here for the first time for diatomic molecular systems. The preexponential factor does not affect the intensity distribution in overtone spectra with the only but important exception where it passes across zero during its slow variation with the energy. The latter results in an anomaly which manifests itself in lowering the intensities (relative to their normal values) of one or two bands in the spectrum nearest in energies to this zero point. The excessively low intensity of the HF $n \leftarrow 0$ absorption at the level $n=6$ as calculated previously by Meredith and Smith is explained in terms of the above effect. Such an anomaly is also predicted here for HCl ($n=4,5$), HBr ($n=3$), HI ($n=1,2$) and CO ($n=5$).

The analytical and numerical tests of the theory are carried out showing the validity of the main conclusions and good accord with the theoretical results of other authors. To compare the theory with experiment, available data on *all diatomic systems* which could be found in literature were used. These are: 1) the overtone absorption spectra of the local CH and CD modes in benzene and its deuterium substituted derivatives as well as the CH absorption data averaged over a number of large polyatomic molecules; 2) the overtone absorption spectra of the local CH modes in halomethanes; 3) the overtone emission spectra of HF, DF and OH; 4) the overtone absorption spectra of HCl, HBr, HI and CO. The normal intensity distribution law is shown to occur in all the experimental overtone spectra considered and the values of the new molecular spectroscopic constant β are determined for all the above diatomic systems. Experimental data also confirm the occurrence of the anomalies in the absorption spectra of HCl, HBr and HI just at those levels predicted by the theory. The anomalies in the HF and DF emission spectra were not revealed, perhaps because of too small energy differences involved in the transitions measured in HF and a too large data scatter in DF. Anomalous lowering the $5 \leftarrow 0$ absorption band intensity is predicted for CO. An attempt to calculate the anomalous band intensities was not successful because of very high sensitivity of the preexponential factor near its zero to the explicit form of the dipole moment function. In principle, this can be used for a more accurate determination of $d(q)$ based on the experimental anomalous band intensities.

1. INTRODUCTION

Molecular spectra in the range of relatively weak vibrational transitions $n \rightleftharpoons m$ at large quantum number differences,

$$n - m \geq 2, m \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

contain information on the behavior of the potential energy $\mathcal{E}(q)$ and the dipole moment $d(q)$ in a wider range of nuclear displacements $q = r - r_e$ than fundamental spectra. The overtone transitions (1) contribute to the emission of diatomic molecules from the states with large vibrational energy ϵ_n and to their absorption from the states of small energy ϵ_m . Emission intensities were measured for OH from the states with $n \leq 10$ at quantum number changes $n - m \leq 7$ [1-10], for HF ($n \leq 9$) and DF ($n \leq 12$) at $n - m \leq 6$ [11]. Intensities of the $n \leftarrow 0$ absorption bands of diatomic molecules were experimentally studied for HF [12-14] ($n \leq 3$), HCl [15-18] ($n \leq 7$), DCI [15] ($n \leq 3$), HBr [19-21] ($n \leq 5$), HI [22-24] ($n \leq 5$), NO [23] ($n \leq 3$), CO [25-27] ($n \leq 4$) and HD [28] ($n = 5$). There are also data on overtone vibrational transitions in the ions HD^+ [29] and HeH^+ [30].

It is well-known that a number of polyatomic molecules absorb radiation in the spectral range of the vibrational overtone transitions like the assemblies of almost independent high-frequency linear anharmonic oscillators, the so-called local modes, corresponding to the stretching vibrations of isolated chemical bonds [31-34]. The experimental evidence in favour of this picture was obtained for the CH bond vibrations in benzene and its derivatives [35-48] as well as in a number of other polyatomic molecules [38, 41, 49-66], and for the OH vibrations in organic molecules [67]. The vibrational overtones of CO in the ground electronic state of benzophenone have recently been observed by emission spectroscopy [68].

Much work has been carried out in recent years to form the theoretical basis for the notion of local modes introduced by Henry and Siebrand [69]. Here are the calculations of vibration spectra of polyatomic molecules [70-80], the investigations of the dynamics of the vibrationally excited molecules by the classical trajectory method [81] and the interpretations of the shape and the fine structure of the overtone absorption bands [82-88].

The basic quantity governing the intensity distribution in the overtone spectrum of a diatomic molecule or a local mode of a polyatomic molecule is the dipole moment matrix element

$$d_{mn} \equiv \langle m | d(q) | n \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \chi_m(q) d(q) \chi_n(q) dq, \quad (2)$$

where $\chi_m(q)$ and $\chi_n(q)$ are the vibrational wave functions in the one-dimensional potential well $\mathcal{E}(q)$. Exact analytical expressions for d_{mn} in the Morse potential were derived by a number of authors if $d(q)$ was a power [89-94] or exponential [94-97] function. In the case of the Morse potential, an asymptotic expansion method was proposed where the matrix element (2) was decomposed in a double sum arising from the usual

representation of the Laguerre polynomials and each integral of this sum was calculated by the saddle-point method [98, 99]. However, the usual way of calculating d_{mn} is to solve the Schrödinger equation numerically using the Morse, RKR or Dunham potential functions and then to perform numerical integration in (2) applying various representations of $d(q)$ [14, 21, 24, 25, 40, 100-108]. Cashion [109] proposed an analytical method based on the expansion of $d(q)$ in terms of the vibrational eigenfunctions [110].

The quasiclassical method can be applied if the vibrational energy ϵ_n is large enough. At small values of the difference $n - m$, the matrix element d_{mn} is expressed, as is well-known [111], in terms of the Fourier coefficient of the function $d(q(t))$ where $q(t)$ is a classical nuclear trajectory corresponding to an intermediate energy value between ϵ_n and ϵ_m . When an average trajectory is introduced to describe quantum transitions the method is called as semiclassical [112]. The semiclassical method was applied to the light absorption accompanied by the vibrational transitions in diatomic molecules in papers [113-116] where it was shown in which way the function $d(q)$ near the equilibrium could be reconstructed from the experimental overtone band intensities. This method is valid at small values of $n - m$ thus giving an information on $d(q)$ only at small displacements from the equilibrium position $q = 0$.

In § 2.1 and 2.2 of the present work, the quasiclassical expression for the matrix elements (2) is derived under the condition that the difference between the vibrational energies of the upper (n) and the lower (m) states greatly exceeds the quantum of the harmonic frequency,

$$y \equiv (\epsilon_n - \epsilon_m) / \hbar \omega \gg 1, m \geq 0. \quad (3)$$

It is deliberately outlined here that the energy of the lower state, ϵ_m , is not subjected to any restrictions. The latter is an essential feature of our approach as compared to the previous applications of the quasiclassical method [111-116] where both the initial and the final states involved in the transition have been supposed to be quasiclassical. As regards the upper state, the condition (1) can often be sufficient at small ϵ_m ; however, at higher values of ϵ_m the first inequality (3) results in larger differences $n - m$ because of an anharmonic level shift.

The simple analytical expression (36) is derived for d_{mn} which is valid for any diatomic potential and any reasonable dipole moment function. A comparison with analytical and numerical results given in § 2.5 shows that the accuracy of this expression is sufficient to enable the analysis of the higher overtone band intensities to be carried out.

Consequences of the theory are examined in § 2.3 and 2.4 from several points of view. First the manner is discussed in which the function $d(q)$ affects the intensity distribution in the overtone spectrum. Ferguson and Parkinson [100] calculated the matrix elements (2) for OH using the Morse potential and various (exponential and polynomial) functions $d(q)$. It was found out that at large values of $n - m$ the ratios of the matrix elements for the transitions from a common level n , $d_{m,n} / d_{m_1,n}$, were very similar regardless to the form of $d(q)$, being very close to their values for the linear function $d(q) = q$. Therefore it was concluded that experimental data

on the higher overtone band intensities could not be used for an accurate determination of the dipole moment function in a wide range of nuclear displacements; only at small $n-m$ the transition intensities are sensitive to the explicit form of $d(q)$, but again only in a close vicinity of the equilibrium. On the other hand, Meredith and Smith [14] made calculations for HF with $d(q)$ in the form of quadratic and cubic polynomials and unexpectedly discovered that while d_{0n}^2 was monotonously decreased with n for the quadratic function there was a deep minimum at $n=6$ for the cubic one, the matrix elements for two functions becoming even opposite in signs at $n>6$. It was thus concluded that the intensities of any transitions with large $n-m$ were strongly dependent upon the explicit form of $d(q)$.

In a number of the above-cited works, the experimental data on the transition intensities with large $n-m$ were handled in a manner aiming at the determination of the function $d(q)$, often giving, however, contradictory results. For example, Burberry and Albrecht [40] took a quadratic Taylor expansion for $d(q)$ and determined its coefficients from a fit of the calculated $n \leftarrow 0$ transition intensities in benzene to the experimental ones at $n \leq 6$. The coefficients thus obtained turned out to be different for benzene- h_6 and benzene- d_6 , which was inconsistent with a static nature of the dipole moment. Sileo and Cool [11] used a Taylor series up to the sixth order in nuclear displacement and calculated the coefficients from the experimental data on the HF emission spectra. Here it is noticeable that increasing the polynomial power from 6 to 8 did not result in a better agreement between the calculated and measured values while the number of data points was great enough to find $d(q)$ with much higher accuracy. Also, the Taylor expansion coefficients of $d(q)$ were quite different between HF and DF.

The present theory shows (§ 2.4 and 2.5) that the transition intensities at large $n-m$ depend very slightly upon the form of $d(q)$, being governed essentially by the potential function, namely by its repulsive portion at small nuclear separations far away from the equilibrium position, $r \ll r_e$, which enters the exponential factor of the transition probability. The dipole moment function $d(q)$ is involved only in the preexponential factor depending insignificantly upon the level energy. Nevertheless in some cases this slowly varying preexponential factor can pass across zero and change its sign (§ 2.6), which explains the anomaly obtained by Meredith and Smith [14]. However, as distinct from these authors, it is asserted here that the above anomaly is local and has not any effect on the intensity distribution in the rest of the spectrum, the latter being dependent only on the potential function as if the anomaly were absent at all. As well, a new conclusion drawn here is that such an anomaly can be experimentally discovered by a significant intensity decrease (or even a complete disappearance) of one or two neighbouring bands in the spectrum if a method of data processing described in § 2.6 is applied.

At the first sight, the above is inconsistent with the fact that Meredith and Smith [14] did not reveal significant differences in the calculated HF results between the Morse and RKR potentials. However, it should be taken

into account that numerical integration of the Schrödinger equation involves the nuclear separations r in the vicinity of the equilibrium separation r_e where two potentials are not much different. In fact, as results from the present theory, very large negative displacements contribute the transition probability where the potential energy $\mathcal{E}(q)$ greatly exceeds the dissociation energy (§ 2.4).

A similar result has been recently obtained by us for the Franck—Condon factors in the theory of the tunnel radiationless transitions [117—119]. The Franck—Condon factors have been shown to be dependent upon the behavior of the potential function in a wide range of nuclear coordinates up to the point of intersection or minimum separation between the potential curves of two electronic states. This enabled us to advance the Franck—Condon principle for radiationless transitions and to explain some trends in the Franck—Condon factors as functions of molecular parameters [119—120]. Heller and Brown [121] have also concluded that the radiationless transition probability was governed by an intersection of the potential curves. If the electronic terms are nearly parallel to one another, as is the case for the CH vibrations in polyatomic molecules, then the points of term intersection move to infinity and the Franck—Condon factors vanish; however, the matrix elements (2) remain finite. Therefore the theory of the present work should be considered as an extension of the quasiclassical method [117—119] to the parallel electronic terms.

Thus it becomes clear that the repulsive part of the diatomic potential $\mathcal{E}(q)$ at large negative displacements rather than the dipole moment function $d(q)$ is to be extracted from the absorption and emission molecular spectra at large values of $n-m$. It is supposed in § 2.3 that $\mathcal{E}(q)$ at $q \rightarrow -\infty$ can be approximated well by an exponential function (43) and an intensity distribution law is derived representing the overtone band intensity as a function of the vibrational energy. The validity of the intensity distribution predicted is supported by a comparison with experiments in § 3 and the values of the new molecular constant β governing the asymptotic behavior of the potential at small interatomic separations are determined for all the diatomic systems studied.

The overtone band intensity distribution derived in § 2.3 is termed here "normal" since it describes a smooth decrease in intensity with $n-m$ caused by the exponential factor in the dipole moment matrix element. The preexponential factor, for which the quasiclassical expression is given here for the first time (see (32), (38) and Appendix), varies very slowly vs. energy and does not affect the normal intensity distribution except the case when it comes across zero at some energy between two successive levels n and $n+1$. In such a case, an anomaly emerges in the spectrum causing an intensity decrease for the bands n and/or $n+1$ relative to their normal values. This effect is thoroughly investigated in § 2.6 where it is shown that the Taylor series given by a number of authors for the functions $d(q)$ of some diatomic molecules often generate such anomalies. The positions of anomalous bands in spectra are predicted there for several molecules.

Certain regularities as noted in [100, 109] occur in sign alternation of the matrix elements d_{mn} if signs of the vibrational wave functions are fixed

by a proper convention. The present theory confirms their general validity but at the same time it shows that the regular sign alternation is broken when the above-mentioned anomaly takes place, i. e. when the slowly varying preexponential function passes through zero. This provides an independent way of determining the anomalous band positions in the absorption spectra (§ 2.6). An analysis of experimental data given in § 3.3 confirms the occurrence of the anomalies in the absorption spectra of diatomic molecules just on those levels predicted by the theory. The results obtained are summarized and discussed in § 4; particularly, an analysis is given of the values derived in § 3 for the new molecular constant β introduced here to describe the repulsive molecular potential at small interatomic separations.

2. THEORY

2.1. Quasiclassical matrix elements in the Morse potential

An expression for the dipole moment matrix elements will be derived here for the Morse potential

$$\mathcal{E}(q) = D(1 - e^{-\alpha q})^2, \quad (4)$$

which will be then extended to arbitrary potentials in § 2.2. The quasiclassical method involves a detailed investigation of the analytic properties of the asymptotics of the wave functions throughout the complex q -plane and a use of a special technique for their analytic continuation across anti-Stokes lines and cuts, which is necessary for choosing the right integration path in (2) and appropriate asymptotic representations for the wave functions along this path. All this work has been earlier done by us in papers [117–119] when solving a similar problem for the Franck–Condon factors in the theory of radiationless transitions, so there is no need in repeating here these and some other details.

Following Landau and Lifshitz [111] we expand the wave function of the upper state in a sum

$$\chi_n(q) = \chi_n^+(q) + \chi_n^-(q), \quad (5)$$

where $\chi_n^\pm(q)$ are exact solutions to the Schrödinger equation decreasing in the upper and lower half-planes respectively. Since they are complex conjugate to one another on the real axis the integral (2) can be recasted in the form

$$d_{mn} = 2\text{Re} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \chi_m(q) d(q) \chi_n^+(q) dq. \quad (6)$$

Now the integration path L is displaced from the real axis into the upper half-plane to avoid turning points, and the wave functions are substituted by their asymptotic representations [117, 119]

$$\chi_m(q) = C_m e_m^-, \quad (7)$$

$$\chi_n^+(q) = e_n^+, \quad (8)$$

where

$$e_n^\pm = \left(\frac{\omega_n}{2\pi v_n} \right)^{1/2} \exp \left(\pm \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{q_n^\pm}^q p_n dq \pm \frac{i\pi}{4} \right), \quad (9)$$

$$C_m = (2\pi)^{1/4} (m!)^{-1/2} \exp \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(m + \frac{1}{2} \right) \ln \left(m + \frac{1}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(m + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right], \quad (10)$$

$$p_n = Mv_n = \sqrt{2M[\epsilon_n - \mathcal{E}(q)]}, \quad (11)$$

$$\omega_n = \omega \left[1 - 2x_e \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right], \quad (12)$$

$$\epsilon_n = \hbar\omega\mu_n = \hbar\omega \left[n + \frac{1}{2} - x_e \left(n + \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (13)$$

M is the reduced mass of two atoms, $\omega = \alpha(2D/M)^{1/2}$ is the harmonic frequency and $x_e = \hbar\omega/4D$ is the usual spectroscopic anharmonicity constant. The branch of the double-valued momentum function (11) is chosen in such a way that $\arg p_n = 0$ on the real axis between the turning points q_n^\pm , $\arg p_n = \pi/2$ on the left from the left turning point

$$q_n^- = -\alpha^{-1} \ln [1 + (\epsilon_n/D)^{1/2}] \quad (14)$$

and $\arg p_n = -\pi/2$ on the right from the right turning point q_n^+ . With this convention, the functions $\chi_m(q)$ and $\chi_n(q)$ are positive on the real axis at $q > q_n^+$ but χ_n^+ is purely imaginary there.

As was shown in [117, 119], the asymptotic expressions (7) and (8) are valid under condition (3). The quantum number m can assume any values including zero since the main contribution to the integral (6) at $n \rightarrow \infty$ comes from the region $\text{Re } q \rightarrow -\infty$ [111] where even the ground state ($m=0$) wave function is quasiclassical. Putting (7)–(9) into (6) one obtains

$$d_{mn} = C_m (\omega_m \omega_n)^{1/2} \alpha (\pi\omega)^{-1} \text{Re} \int_L d(q) \exp[\Psi(q)] dq, \quad (15)$$

$$\Psi(q) = -\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{q_m^+}^q p_m dq + \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{q_n^+}^q p_n dq - \ln [(v_m v_n)^{1/2} \alpha / \omega]. \quad (16)$$

The integral (15) is evaluated by the saddle-point method. The saddle point q_* is a root of the equation

$$\Psi'(q) \equiv 2iM\omega \frac{\mu_n - \mu_m}{p_m + p_n} - \frac{v'_m}{2v_m} - \frac{v'_n}{2v_n} = 0. \quad (17)$$

At $\text{Re } q \rightarrow -\infty$ the approximate relations

$$p_m = p_n = Mv_m = Mv_n = (2MD)^{1/2} \exp \left(\frac{i\pi}{2} - \alpha q \right) \quad (18)$$

hold and equation (17) becomes

$$\Psi'(q) \equiv \alpha y e^{\alpha q} + \alpha = 0, \quad (19)$$

$$y \equiv \mu_n - \mu_m = (n - m) [1 - x_e(n + m + 1)]. \quad (20)$$

Hence the saddle point in the upper half-plane nearest to the real axis is

$$q_* = (i\pi - \ln y)/\alpha. \quad (21)$$

The behavior of $\Psi(q)$ in the vicinity of q_* can be determined by integrating relation (19),

$$\Psi(q) \equiv \Psi(q_*) + \int_{q_*}^q \Psi'(q) dq = \Psi(q_*) + 1 + \alpha(q - q_*) - \exp[\alpha(q - q_*)]. \quad (22)$$

Change the integration variable in the integral (15) to $t = \alpha(q - q_*)$ and introduce the notations

$$x \equiv \alpha q, \quad V(x) \equiv d(q), \quad (23)$$

where $V(x)$ is the dipole moment function of the dimensionless nuclear displacement x . The integration limits can be taken equal to $\pm \infty$ due to fast convergence of the integral. Substituting (22) and (23) into (15) gives

$$d_{mn} = C_m (\omega_m \omega_n)^{1/2} (\pi\omega)^{-1} \text{Re} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} V(xq_* + t) \exp[\Psi(q_*) + 1 + t - e^t] dt. \quad (24)$$

Here the expression $\Psi(q_*)$ still remains to be calculated from (16). Write it down as

$$\Psi(q_*) \equiv I_m^{(1)} + I_m^{(2)} - I_n^{(1)} - I_n^{(2)} + I^{(3)} + I^{(4)}, \quad (25)$$

where the first item equals to

$$I_m^{(1)} \equiv -\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{q_m^+}^{q_m^-} p_m dq = i\pi \left(m + \frac{1}{2}\right) \quad (26)$$

according to the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantization rule and

$$I_m^{(2)} \equiv -\delta_m \equiv \frac{1}{\hbar} \int_{q_m^-}^{\text{Re} q_*} |p_m| dq; \quad (27)$$

similar expressions are obtained for $I_n^{(1)}$ and $I_n^{(2)}$. Other terms in (25) are calculated approximately using (18) and (21),

$$I^{(3)} \equiv -\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_{\text{Re} q_*}^{q_*} (p_m - p_n) dq = 2iM\omega y \int_{\text{Re} q_*}^{q_*} \frac{dq}{p_m + p_n} = -2, \quad (28)$$

$$I^{(4)} \equiv -\ln[(v_m v_n)^{1/2} \alpha / \omega] = \frac{i\pi}{2} - \ln y.$$

Inserting (25)–(28) into (24) and changing the integration variable $t = \ln z$ we come to the final result, which is conveniently represented as two separate relations. The first one is written for the linear dipole moment function $V(x) = x$,

$$\langle m | x | n \rangle = (-1)^{n-m} C_m (\omega_m \omega_n)^{1/2} (\omega y)^{-1} \exp(S_{mn}), \quad (29)$$

and the second is for an arbitrary function $V(x)$

$$\langle m | V(x) | n \rangle = \rho[V(x), y] \langle m | x | n \rangle, \quad (30)$$

where

$$S_{mn} = \delta_n - \delta_m - 1, \quad (31)$$

$$\rho[V(x), y] = \text{Re} (i\pi)^{-1} \int_0^\infty V(i\pi - \ln y + \ln z) e^{-z} dz, \quad (32)$$

and y is the vibrational energy difference between the initial and final states divided by $\hbar\omega$ (see (20) and (13)). The real positive parameters δ_n and δ_m can be calculated from the accurate formulae given in [118, 119], which get simplified in the limiting case (3) giving the following expression for S_{mn} :

$$S_{mn} = \left(\sigma - \frac{1}{2}n + \frac{1}{4}\right) \ln(2\sigma - n) - \left(\sigma - \frac{1}{2}m + \frac{1}{4}\right) \ln(2\sigma - m) + \frac{1}{2} \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) \ln n - \frac{1}{2} \left(m + \frac{1}{2}\right) \ln \left(m + \frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{4}, \quad (33)$$

where

$$\sigma = (x_e^{-1} - 1)/2. \quad (34)$$

Equations (29)–(32) are the main result of this section. In deriving them, the function $V(x)$ itself has been assumed to be smooth enough, having no singularities in a finite part of the complex plane which could interfere with the saddle point q_* . The condition for their validity was given in the form of the inequality (3) used in the above derivation as a requirement of $\text{Re} q_* \rightarrow -\infty$. The least necessary condition is that q_* would be situated on the left from the left turning point, $\text{Re} q_* < q_n^-$. Using (13), (14), (20) and (21), write it down in the form

$$y \equiv (\varepsilon_n - \varepsilon_m)/\hbar\omega > 1 + (\varepsilon_n/D)^{1/2}. \quad (35)$$

This inequality does not surely hold for the fundamental band $n-m=1$ since its left-hand side is smaller than unity because of the anharmonic level shift. At any given value of $n-m \geq 2$, it is satisfied for small n but with n rising the left-hand side of (35) falls due to anharmonicity and the right-hand one increases. Therefore, given a succession of level pairs with a fixed difference $n-m$, there exists a maximum value of m above which the inequality (35) breaks down. However, at a given value of m it is satisfied the better, the higher n is.

2.2. Quasiclassical matrix elements in an arbitrary potential

Landau and Lifshitz [111] have derived a general expression for quasiclassical matrix elements in an arbitrary potential, but with no preexponential factor. The exponential part of this expression includes the difference between classical actions from turning points to a point $q=q_0$ where the potential is singular. Being applied to a diatomic potential, which gene-

rally tends to infinity only at a large negative nuclear displacement $q=q_0$, the Landau—Lifshitz formula becomes

$$d_{mn} \equiv \langle m | d(q) | n \rangle = Q \exp(S_{mn}), \quad (36)$$

where Q is a slow function of quantum numbers and

$$S_{mn} \equiv \lim_{q \rightarrow q_0} \left(\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_{q_m}^q |p_m| dq - \frac{1}{\hbar} \int_{q_n}^q |p_n| dq \right). \quad (37)$$

For the Morse potential (4), the quasiclassical expression (29) has been derived in § 2.1 which is similar to (36) but with S_{mn} defined by relations (27) and (31). For this potential we have $q_0 = -\infty$ and (31) would appear to be different from (37). In fact, these two expressions for S_{mn} are identical because their difference is

$$\frac{1}{\hbar} \int_{\text{Re} q_*}^{-\infty} (|p_m| - |p_n|) dq + 1 = 2M\omega y \int_{\text{Re} q_*}^{-\infty} \frac{dq}{|p_m| + |p_n|} + 1 \approx \approx -y \exp(\alpha \text{Re} q_*) + 1 = 0,$$

where relations (18) and (21) were used. Hence, equations (29) and (30) obtained in § 2.1 for the Morse potential are a specific case of the general formula (36) valid for any diatomic potential. Deriving them in § 2.1 has aimed to find out the preexponential factor Q which, according to (29) and (30), is given by

$$Q = (-1)^{n-m-1} C_m (\omega_m \omega_n)^{1/2} (\omega y)^{-1} \rho [V(x), y]. \quad (38)$$

A similar expression could be presumably obtained for an arbitrary potential as well. For example, in general ω_n is the frequency of classical vibrations at energy ϵ_n and C_m is at all near independent of the potential used, being only slightly different from the unity [117, 119]. As for the factor ρ , it is a more complicated matter since (32) is no longer valid. To find ρ one has to solve an equation for the saddle point q_* in a given potential and then to calculate integral (15) near q_* .

In reality, however, such a generalization has not any meaning since all the factors in (38) are slow functions of quantum numbers as compared to the exponential factor of (36). It is obvious regarding y , ω_m , ω_n and C_m . The fact that ρ depends only weakly on quantum numbers as well is an important result of the present theory. It will be thoroughly discussed in § 2.4 and checked by analytical and numerical methods in § 2.5. Here we would like only to note that ρ is a logarithmic function of the energy difference y if $V(x)$ rises with $|x|$ not faster than a polynomial, the dependence of ρ on y being even weaker if $V(x)$ decreases (see (32)). It should be noted as well that for a sequence $n-m=\text{const}$ the energy difference y itself is nearly constant and therefore ρ can be regarded as a constant so much the more.

Thus in the general case of the arbitrary diatomic potential, the dipole moment matrix elements are given by expressions (36)—(38) where all the quantities except S_{mn} are to be calculated by the equations given in § 2.1

for the Morse potential. By the diatomic potential we mean that one which tends to a dissociation limit at $q \gg 0$ and grows at $q \ll 0$ faster than q^2 (the latter condition arises from expression (37) which diverges for slow potentials).

2.3. Normal intensity distributions in overtone spectra

The dipole moment matrix element squared $f_{mn} = d_{mn}^2$ governs the intensity of radiation emission and absorption due to overtone transitions $n \rightleftharpoons m$. For brevity, the quantity f_{mn} itself will be called here as the intensity.

For any three quantum numbers $n > m_1 > m_2$ the following general relation results from (36) and (37):

$$\ln(f_{m_1 n} / f_{m_2 n}) = 2(S_{m_1 n} - S_{m_2 n}) = 2S_{m_1 m_2}. \quad (39)$$

Here and below in this section the weak dependence of Q upon the quantum numbers is disregarded. It is predicted by (39) that the **emission intensity ratio from a common level n is independent of n** . This will be compared with experiment in § 3.2.

Let us now find out the dependence of the intensity upon the upper level energy ϵ_n . According to (36) and (37), one has

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \epsilon_n} \ln f_{mn} = 2 \frac{\partial S_{mn}}{\partial \epsilon_n} = \frac{\sqrt{2M}}{\hbar} \int_{q_n}^{q_0} \frac{dq}{\sqrt{\mathcal{E}(q) - \epsilon_n}}. \quad (40)$$

where the limit $q \rightarrow q_0$ is directly set, the potential $\mathcal{E}(q)$ being supposed to tend to infinity fast enough to ensure convergence of the integral (40). The derivative with respect to its lower limit contributes nothing since q_n is a turning point.

Changing the integration variable

$$z = \sqrt{\mathcal{E}(q) - \epsilon_n}, \quad 2z dz = \mathcal{E}'(q) dq \equiv -F(q) dq \quad (41)$$

transforms (40) to

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \epsilon_n} \ln f_{mn} = -\frac{2\sqrt{2M}}{\hbar} \int_0^\infty \frac{dz}{F(q)}, \quad (42)$$

where q is a function of z and ϵ_n given by (41).

Further it is assumed that the repulsive potential at large negative displacements q can be approximated by a smooth function monotonously increasing at $q \rightarrow -\infty$ (i. e. $q_0 = -\infty$). Consider two typical approximations.

1. The approximation by an exponential function

$$\mathcal{E}(q) \rightarrow C \exp(-2\beta q). \quad (43)$$

For it one has from (41)

$$F(q) = 2\beta \mathcal{E}(q) = 2\beta(z^2 + \epsilon_n). \quad (44)$$

Substituting this into (42) and making use of (13), one gets by trivial manipulations

$$\ln f_{mn} = \text{const} - \lambda \sqrt{\nu_n}, \quad (45)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\pi}{\beta} \left(\frac{2M\omega}{\hbar} \right)^{1/2} = \frac{\pi}{\beta r_e} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega}{B} \right)^{1/2}, \quad (46)$$

where r_e is the equilibrium nuclear separation, $B = \hbar^2/2Mr_e^2$ is the rotational constant and const is a function of only the quantum number m .

If, besides the general condition (3) for validity of the quasiclassical method, an additional condition

$$\varepsilon_m \gg \hbar\omega, \quad (47)$$

holds as well, the above derivation can be repeated regarding the dependence of f_{mn} upon the lower level energy ε_m , which gives the well-known result by Landau and Lifshitz [111] (see problem 1 to § 51)

$$\ln f_{mn} = \text{const} - \lambda (\sqrt{\nu_n} - \sqrt{\nu_m}). \quad (48)$$

The relative intensities (39) treated in the same way at large n and m_1 become

$$\ln (f_{m_1n}/f_{m_2n}) = \lambda \sqrt{\nu_{m_1}} + \text{const}, \quad (49)$$

where const depends on m_2 alone. Finally, if m_2 is large as well one obtains from (48)

$$\ln (f_{m_1n}/f_{m_2n}) = \lambda (\sqrt{\nu_{m_1}} - \sqrt{\nu_{m_2}}). \quad (50)$$

In all these expressions λ is still given by (46).

2. The approximation by a power function

$$\mathcal{E}(q) = C(-2\beta q)^k. \quad (51)$$

From (41) one gets

$$F(q) = 2k\beta C^{1/k} (z^2 + \varepsilon_n)^{(k-1)/k}. \quad (52)$$

Substituting (52) into (42) and integrating leads to

$$\ln f_{mn} = \text{const} - \tilde{\lambda} \nu_n^{1/2+1/k}, \quad (53)$$

where $\tilde{\lambda}$ is a constant. At $k \gg 1$ this energy dependence is only slightly different from that of (45) for the exponential function. Hence we may assert that the intensity distribution predicted by (45) is general enough. Experimental verification to equations (45), (49) and (50) will be given in § 3.

Equation (46) predicts a small deuterium isotope effect on the intensity distribution in overtone spectra. Actually, taking into account that $\omega \sim M^{-1/2}$ we get from (46)

$$\lambda \sim M^{1/4}. \quad (54)$$

It is seen as well that for the molecules without light atoms (H or D) the value of λ will be large and the band intensities will decrease very steeply with increasing $n-m$.

In conclusion, it should be stressed that equation (39) is the most accurate one since only the general condition (3) for the validity of the

theory has been involved in its derivation. Therefore it holds at any quantum numbers $m_1 > m_2 \geq 0$. Equations (45) and (48)–(50) are approximate in the sense that they are subjected to an additional restriction resulting from the approximation (43) for the potential function. Among them (45) is the most accurate, being valid at any $m \geq 0$. It is followed by equations (48) and (49) restricted by a further assumption, m and $m_1 \gg 1$. Finally, equation (50) is applicable only when m_1 and $m_2 \gg 1$.

These relations will be called here as **normal intensity distributions** in overtone spectra since they describe smooth intensity variations with quantum numbers provided by the exponential factor of the dipole moment matrix element (36). These distributions depend only upon the potential function $\mathcal{E}(q)$. Possible violations of the normal distribution caused by the preexponential factor (38) involving the dipole moment function $d(q)$ will be discussed in § 2.6.

2.4. Other consequences of the theory

In § 2.3 the quantitative relations (39), (45) and (48)–(50) have been derived to be compared with experiment (see § 3). Additionally, the theory yields important qualitative results, which can be verified by both numerical calculations and a comparison with numerical results of other authors (see § 2.5 and 2.6).

An essential qualitative result following from (36) is that the dipole moment matrix elements decrease exponentially with $n-m$ at fixed m , being proportional to $\exp(S_{mn})$ where S_{mn} depends only on the potential function $\mathcal{E}(q)$. The dipole moment function $d(q)$ enters only the preexponential factor Q through the functional ρ (see (38) and (23)) which varies very slowly with the energy difference y between the upper and the lower states. Namely, ρ is a logarithmic function of y if $d(q)$ increases not faster than a power of q at $|q| \rightarrow \infty$ (see (32)).

The matrix elements d_{mn} are usually supposed [14, 40, 109, 115, 116] to be influenced more by the choice of $d(q)$ than that of $\mathcal{E}(q)$. It is certainly true for low quantum numbers because the main contribution to the integral (2) arises in the close vicinity of the potential minimum where various functions $\mathcal{E}(q)$ nearly coincide with one another. However, as results from the present theory, at large values of $n-m$ the matrix elements (2) depend on the potential behavior at large negative displacements q up to Req_* . To make clear what range of displacements and energies is implied, let us perform simple estimates for the CH vibrations in benzene using the Morse potential. Letting $m=0$, $\hbar\omega=3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $D=44000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\alpha=1.77 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, we get from (21) $Req_* = -0.36 \text{ \AA}$ at $n=2$ and -0.58 \AA at $n=3$. At such displacements the potential energy (4) in units of the dissociation energy is $\mathcal{E}(q)/D=0.8$ at $n=2$ and 3.2 at $n=3$. Obviously, any two potential functions close to one another near the minimum will be quite different at such enormous displacements. That is why the situation is just opposite at large $n-m$, i. e. d_{mn} is strongly affected by $\mathcal{E}(q)$ and only slightly by $d(q)$. Hence it follows that the potential function $\mathcal{E}(q)$ at

large negative displacements rather than $d(q)$ is to be determined from the overtone spectra.

As was said in § 1, an insignificant effect of $d(q)$ on d_{mn} has been already noted in reference [100] but Meredith and Smith [14] have come to an opposite result. These authors have calculated the HF dipole moment matrix elements fitting $d(q)$ by quadratic and cubic polynomials of q and $\mathcal{E}(q)$ by the Morse and RKR functions. In all cases the matrix elements calculated with two potential functions were not very much different (at least for not too large values of $n-m$), which is undoubtedly due to restrictions involved in the numerical algorithm for solving the Schrödinger equation with the numerical RKR potential available for HF only at displacements $q > -0.2 \text{ \AA}$ and at energies lower than D . More important in our opinion is the fact that the matrix elements d_{0n} for the quadratic function $d(q)$ decrease smoothly with n as opposed to those for the cubic one exhibiting an anomaly at $n=6$ both in the absolute magnitude and in the sign.

Equation (30) shows that any anomaly, i. e. a significant violation of the smooth normal distribution derived in § 2.3 can result only from variation of ρ with y because, as follows from (29), the matrix element of the linear dipole moment, $\langle m | x | n \rangle$, is a smooth function of quantum numbers. Since ρ depends only weakly on y it should be expected to keep its sign unchanged over a wide range of quantum numbers, which corresponds to the normal intensity distribution. However, in principle the slow function ρ may cross zero and change its sign near some level n (at a fixed value of m). This is exactly the origin of the anomaly obtained in [14]. Whether this explanation is right can be checked by evaluating ρ according to (32) and by comparing the results with the computer calculations by Meredith and Smith [14]. This will be done in § 2.6 giving the result that the functional ρ calculated from (32) for the cubic dipole moment $d(q)$ with the same coefficients as given in [14] indeed goes across zero and just at n near 6. If such a behavior can be met in reality it will manifest itself experimentally in an intensity decrease or even in complete disappearance from the spectrum of one or two neighbouring bands near which ρ is anomalously low.

The functional ρ exhibits a remarkable feature of being universal. Namely, for a given dipole moment function $V(x)$ (see definition (23)) it is a function of only the energy difference y , being independent of both the quantum number n (or m) and the molecular constants separately. If the present theory is valid, the same feature should be characteristic of the ratio of the exact matrix elements,

$$R[V(x), y] \equiv \frac{\langle m | V(x) | n \rangle}{\langle m | x | n \rangle}, \quad (55)$$

calculated either from available analytical expressions or numerically. This result is far from being evident and we shall check it by analytical and numerical methods in § 2.5.

A further consequence of equations (29)–(32) regards to the signs of the matrix elements. Cashion [109] and Ferguson and Parkinson [100] have

formulated a rule that the signs of the matrix elements d_{mn} are the same within any sequence $n-m=\text{const}$. Now we can assert that this rule is a general one, being valid for any functions $\mathcal{E}(q)$ and $d(q)$. Indeed, according to (29) this rule is satisfied for the matrix elements of the linear dipole moment function. As for arbitrary dipole moment functions, it could be broken down because of a change in sign of ρ ; however, the value of y is nearly independent of n at $n-m=\text{const}$ so that ρ can change its sign only at very large values of n .

One more rule can be derived from equations (29) and (30) regarding to the signs of the overtone absorption matrix elements d_{0n} . Namely, in the normal case, when ρ does not vanish with changing n , the signs of the matrix elements d_{0n} alternate successively. For example, at $\rho > 0$ we have the sign succession (+ - + - + - + - + -) for $n=1, 2, \dots, 10$. On the other hand, this succession will be changed if the anomaly appears. Let ρ cross zero somewhere between the levels $n=5$ and 6. Then, according to (29) and (30), the sign succession will be following: (+ - + - + + - + - +). Exactly this sign succession is seen in the HF dipole moment matrix elements calculated by Meredith and Smith [14] (see their table in Appendix 2 and our table 4). This effect will be discussed further in § 2.6.

2.5. Analytical and numerical tests of the theory

This section presents some results enabling to estimate the accuracy of the quasiclassical approximation and to test the predictions of the theory.

An exact expression for the matrix elements of the linear dipole moment function have been derived for the Morse potential in papers [89–91, 94]. In our notations it is

$$\langle m | x | n \rangle = (-1)^{n-m-1} (\omega_m \omega_n)^{1/2} (\omega y)^{-1} \left[\frac{n! \Gamma(2\sigma - n + 1)}{m! \Gamma(2\sigma - m + 1)} \right]^{1/2}, \quad (56)$$

where σ is given by (34), y by (20) and $\Gamma(z)$ is the gamma function. In the quasiclassical limit (3), this expression must coincide with (29). Since the energy levels in the discrete spectrum satisfy the condition $n < \sigma$ and the parameter σ is large, we can transform (56) using the Stirling formula at $n \gg 1, 2\sigma - n \gg 1, 2\sigma - m \gg 1$. Then it is a simple matter to see that (56) becomes identical with (29) where S_{mn} is to be replaced by its approximate expression (33).

For an arbitrary function $V(x)$, the matrix elements are expressed as the product (30) of the linear function matrix elements and of the functional ρ , for which the expression (32) has been obtained. The latter is now to be compared with the ratio (55) of the exact matrix elements.

For the exponential function $V(x) = e^{-x}$, an exact analytical expression has been derived in [94, 96], from which it follows that

$$R[e^{-x}, y] = -y. \quad (57)$$

On the other hand, calculating ρ from (32) for a general exponential function $V(x) = e^{-vx}$ with $v < 1$ gives

$$\rho[e^{-vx}, y] = -y^v / \Gamma(v). \quad (58)$$

Virtually this holds at any values of ν because its right-hand side is nonsingular at $\nu \gg 1$. Obviously, at $\nu=1$ it is identical with the exact analytical result (57). Of course, such a literal coincidence is occasional and in general only an approximate equality between ρ and R can be expected. Thus comparing (58) with the corresponding exact expression [94] gives a relative error of the order of $1/(n-m)$. For example, at $\nu=2$ one gets from (58)

$$\rho[e^{-2x}, y] = -y^2 \approx -(n-m)^2, \quad (59)$$

and the exact expression [94] gives

$$R[e^{-2x}, y] \approx -(n-m)(n-m+1) \quad (60)$$

the small terms $\sim 1/\sigma$ being omitted in both the equations. Equations (59) and (60) demonstrate both the remarkable insensitivity of the preexponential factor to the form of the dipole moment function and the excellent accuracy of the quasiclassical approximation. As a matter of fact, even for a function that increases exponentially just within the region providing the main contribution to the integral (2) (i. e. at $x \rightarrow -\infty$, as was shown in § 2.1), the two-fold increase in the exponent range parameter results in increasing R by a factor of $n-m+1$ (the latter being, of course, of no importance as compared with the exponential factor of (36)), which is nearly exactly reproduced by the quasiclassical expression (59).

One more exact result following from (32),

$$\rho[1, y] = 0, \quad (61)$$

should be noted. This is obviously just as must be for the overlap integral of two vibrational functions with $n > m$, to which the matrix element (2) reduces at $d(q) = \text{const}$.

To gain a more complete idea of the accuracy of the quasiclassical formulae (29)–(32), we have carried out numerical calculations of the matrix elements in the Morse potential for both the power functions

$$V_k(x) = x^k \quad \text{at } k=1, 2, 3 \quad (62)$$

and the exponential ones

$$\begin{aligned} V_F(x) &= \exp(-x/2), \\ V_A(x) &= (1-a_1x)\exp(-a_2x^2) \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

The function $V_A(x)$ has been proposed in [40] as a more realistic one as compared with the power expansions.

Exact values of the matrix elements were calculated by direct numerical integration with the Morse wave functions expressed through Laguerre polynomials. The signs were chosen in such a way that $\chi_n(q) > 0$ as $q \rightarrow +\infty$. The matrix elements of the linear function $V_1(x)$ were additionally calculated from equation (56) to inspect the accuracy of the numerical integration procedure, which in all cases ensured the first five significant figures. Although there are exact analytical expressions for $V_2(x)$ [91, 94], $V_3(x)$ and $V_F(x)$ [94], they were not used because they are too cumbersome.

The following values of the parameters for the local CH stretching vibrations in benzene were used in the numerical calculations: the parameters in the Birge–Sponer relation

$$\epsilon_m - \epsilon_0 = m(A + Bm) \quad (64)$$

were $A = 3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $B = -57.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [47]; the effective mass (the reduced mass of CH) $M = 0.930 \text{ a. u.}$ [122]; the Morse parameter

$$\alpha = \sqrt{-2MB/\hbar} = 1.77 \text{ \AA}^{-1}; \quad (65)$$

the parameters of the function $V_A(x)$ were $a_1\alpha = 1.35 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ and $a_2\alpha^2 = 1.0 \text{ \AA}^{-2}$ [40].

The calculated values of the matrix elements of the linear function and those of the relative matrix elements of the exponential functions are shown in table 1. The second column contains the energy differences y in units of $\hbar\omega$ and the third one shows the matrix elements of the linear function $V_1(x) = x$. The upper entry of each site in the third column is an exact value of the matrix element and the lower entry is a quasiclassical one calculated by equations (27), (29) and (31). The fourth and the fifth columns present the relative matrix elements of the exponential functions (63); the upper entry of each site is an exact value R by equation (55) and the lower entry is the quasiclassical one ρ by equation (32).

Table 1 shows that the accuracy of the quasiclassical method sharply increases with y . For higher overtone transitions, excellent agreement between the quasiclassical and exact results is seen for both the matrix elements and their ratios. As should be expected, the errors become larger when y decreases. Table 1 does not include the transitions which do not satisfy the least necessary condition (35) for the validity of the theory. The relative deviations Δ for the matrix elements of the linear function in the third column are distributed as follows: $\Delta \leq 17\%$ at $y > 4$ (18 entries), $\Delta = 18 \div 34\%$ at $y = 3 \div 4$ (13 entries) and $\Delta > 37\%$ at $y < 3$ (14 entries, the largest deviation being by a factor of 1.5 to 2).

A similar picture is seen for the relative matrix elements of the exponential functions. The differences in column 4 are negligible. In column 5 they are appreciably higher, nevertheless being reasonable and fastly decreasing when y increases. At small y significant anomalies caused by vanishing the factor ρ are present (see § 2.4 and 2.6).

However, the most important result obtained in table 1 consists in supporting the conclusion drawn in § 2.4 that the relative matrix elements (55) are very slow functions of $n-m$. For example, at $m=0$ and $n=4-10$ the ratios R in columns 4 and 5 vary less than by a factor of 1.5 whereas the absolute value of the matrix element $\langle m|x|n \rangle$ varies over three orders of magnitude.

Figure 1 shows the numerical results for the relative matrix elements of the power functions (62). Full lines are the quasiclassical functions $\rho[x^k, y]$ vs. y at $k=2$ and 3 calculated by equation (32). These functions are explicitly given in Appendix. Bearing in mind the least necessary condition (35) for the validity of the theory, we plotted these functions only at

Table 1

Comparison of the quasiclassical (lower entry in each site) and exact (upper entry) matrix elements of the linear function (third column) and of the matrix element's ratios for exponential functions (the fourth and fifth columns) calculated for the local CH vibrations in benzene using the Morse potential

$m-n$	y	$\langle m x n\rangle$	R and ρ for		$m-n$	y	$\langle m x n\rangle$	R and ρ for	
			$V_E(x)$	$V_A(x)$				$V_E(x)$	$V_A(x)$
1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
0-2	1,89	-1,31-02 -2,08-02	-0,73 -0,78	-0,25 -0,07*	1-10	7,05	5,03-06 5,46-06	-1,47 -1,50	1,87 2,00
0-3	2,78	2,10-03 2,70-03	-0,90 -0,94	0,71 1,76*	2-4	1,75	-3,34-02 -6,05-02	-0,70 -0,75	-0,43 -0,46*
0-4	3,64	-4,35-04 -5,24-04	-1,04 -1,08	1,46 2,57	2-5	2,57	7,02-03 9,40-03	-0,86 -0,90	0,47 1,42*
0-5	4,46	1,10-04 1,27-04	-1,16 -1,19	1,89 2,77	2-6	3,35	-1,83-03 -2,24-03	-1,00 -1,03	1,25 2,38
0-6	5,24	-3,20-05 -3,59-05	-1,26 -1,29	2,05 2,67	2-7	4,10	5,57-04 6,51-04	-1,11 -1,14	1,75 2,74
0-7	5,99	1,04-05 1,15-05	-1,35 -1,38	2,04 2,43	2-8	4,81	-1,90-04 -2,16-04	-1,21 -1,24	2,00 2,75
0-8	6,70	-3,73-06 -4,07-06	-1,43 -1,46	1,94 2,15	2-9	5,48	7,16-05 7,99-05	-1,29 -1,32	2,08 2,60
0-9	7,37	1,45-06 1,57-06	-1,51 -1,53	1,79 1,86	2-10	6,12	-2,93-05 -3,23-05	-1,37 -1,40	2,04 2,38
0-10	8,01	-6,12-07 -6,57-07	-1,57 -1,60	1,62 1,59	3-5	1,67	-1,40-02 -9,06-02	-0,68 -0,73	-0,51 -0,66*
1-3	1,82	-2,32-02 -3,88-02	-0,71 -0,76	-0,34 -0,26*	3-6	2,46	1,02-02 1,40-02	-0,84 -0,88	0,34 1,22*
1-4	2,67	4,31-03 5,65-03	-0,88 -0,92	0,59 1,60*	3-7	3,20	-2,91-03 -3,61-03	-0,97 -1,01	1,12 2,26
1-5	3,49	-1,02-03 -1,23-03	-1,02 -1,05	1,36 2,49	3-8	3,91	9,56-04 1,13-03	-1,08 -1,12	1,65 2,69
1-6	4,28	2,84-04 3,28-04	-1,13 -1,17	1,82 2,76	3-9	4,59	-3,50-04 -4,01-04	-1,18 -1,21	1,95 2,77
1-7	5,02	-8,97-05 -1,01-04	-1,23 -1,26	2,03 2,72	3-10	5,23	1,40-04 1,58-04	-1,26 -1,29	2,07 2,67
1-8	5,73	3,15-05 3,50-05	-1,32 -1,35	2,07 2,52	4-7	2,35	1,39-02 1,98-02	-0,82 -0,87	0,21 1,01*
1-9	6,41	-1,21-05 -1,33-05	-1,40 -1,43	2,00 2,27	4-8	3,06	-4,29-03 -5,41-03	-0,95 -0,99	0,99 2,11

1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
4-9	3,73	1,51-03 1,80-03	-1,06 -1,09	1,55 2,62	5-10	3,55	2,25-03 2,72-03	-1,03 -1,06	1,42 2,53
4-10	4,37	-5,88-04 -6,80-04	-1,15 -1,18	1,88 2,77	6-9	2,13	2,29-02 3,57-02	-0,78 -0,82	-0,06 0,54*
5-8	2,24	1,82-02 2,68-02	-0,80 -0,84	0,07 0,78*	6-10	2,77	-8,07-03 -1,06-02	-0,90 -0,94	0,68 1,75
5-9	2,91	-5,59-03 -7,71-03	-0,93 -0,96	0,84 1,94	7-10	2,02	2,83-02 4,73-02	-0,76 -0,80	-0,20 0,27*

* The anomalies in the matrix elements of the function $V_A(x)$ caused by variations of the factor $\rho[V_A(x), y]$ as a function of y , which goes across zero somewhere within the interval of $y=1.75-2.78$ (see § 2.6). The quasiclassical approximation should not be used for calculating the transition intensities involving two adjacent levels between which a zero of the factor ρ occurs (see the end of § 3.3). Note: $-1,31-02$ means $-1,31 \cdot 10^{-2}$.

$y \geq 1.2$. Empty circles are the exact ratios of the matrix elements (55) calculated by us for the local CH vibrations in benzene at $n-m \leq 6$, $n \leq 9$ and crosses are those for hydroxyl radical OH from paper [100].

Fig. 1. Comparison of the quasiclassical and exact matrix elements ratios for the power dipole moment functions $V(x)=x^2$ (the bottom panel) and $V(x)=x^3$ (the top panel). Full lines are the quasiclassical universal functions $\rho[V(x), y]$ calculated by equations (A4), (A5) and (A14) of Appendix; crosses and circles are the exact matrix element's ratios $R[V(x), y]$ from (55) at different n and m ($n \leq 9$, $n-m \leq 6$). X: the Ferguson and Parkinson's [100] results for OH ($x_e=0.02201$); O: our results for the local CH vibrations in benzene ($x_e=0.01809$). The abscissa is the energy difference between two levels n and m in $\hbar\omega$ units (see (20)).

The results presented in figure 1 confirm the predictions of the theory outlined in § 2.4. It is first seen that the ratios (55) of the matrix elements are universal functions of the only parameter y since, given the dipole moment function $V(x)$, all points for CH and OH at various values of n and m turn out to lie along a unique smooth curve which is very close to the corresponding quasiclassical one. Hence, these ratios indeed are independent of both the molecular parameter x_e and the quantum numbers n and m separately, being functions only of the energy difference y . It should be stressed that this result is far from being evident and it conclusively supports the present theory. In fact, extensive numerical tables of

the dipole moment matrix elements have been published in a number of the papers cited in § 1 but only the present work shows for the first time that the ratios of the matrix elements are universal functions of only one parameter y .

Also confirmed is the second conclusion that the relative matrix elements are slow functions of quantum numbers. Within the range of y indicated in figure 1, these ratios vary in very limited intervals whereas the matrix elements of the linear function are changed over several orders of magnitude (see table 1). This is also a very important result of the theory indicating that the intensity distribution in the higher overtone spectrum is nearly insensitive to the explicit form of the dipole moment function and therefore can not be used for precise determination of this function.

One more inference to be of interest can be drawn by inspection of figure 1. It is seen that the slow function $\rho[x^3, y]$ crosses zero at $y \approx 2$ whereas the function $\rho[x^2, y]$ does not vanish anywhere. For the slowly varying function, as normal should be considered such a behavior when it does not pass across zero retaining its sign unchanged. That is why we shall say that $\rho[x^3, y]$ exhibits an anomaly at $y \approx 2$. Obviously, the intensity distribution at anomalous values of y is sharply different from the normal one and, as distinct from the latter, is governed by the dipole moment function rather than the potential. This effect is discussed in the next section.

2.6. Anomalies in matrix elements

An anomaly in the dipole moment matrix elements was first discovered by Meredith and Smith [14] who numerically calculated the matrix elements for two approximations of the HF dipole moment function,

$$d_k(q) = \sum_{i=0}^k d_{ki} q^i, \quad (66)$$

where $k=2$ or 3 . The coefficients d_{ki} were found in [14] through a fit of the calculated matrix elements $\langle 0 | d_k(q) | n \rangle$ to the experimental values from the HF overtone absorption intensities at $n \leq 3$. For $\mathcal{E}(q)$, the Morse or RKR potential was used. They found that the matrix elements of the quadratic function $d_2(q)$ for the transitions $n \leftarrow 0$ decreased monotonously with increasing n but those of the cubic function $d_3(q)$ exhibited an anomaly at $n=6$, i. e. the $6 \leftarrow 0$ matrix element was very small in absolute magnitude and at $n > 6$ even the signs became reversed relative to the signs of the corresponding matrix elements of the function $d_2(q)$. On this ground Meredith and Smith, as well as other authors [40], came at the conclusion that the intensity distribution in the overtone spectrum was strongly dependent upon the explicit form of the function $d(q)$. On the other hand, we have shown in § 2.5 that $d(q)$ can affect the intensity distribution only in a particular case when the corresponding functional ρ vanishes at some value of the energy difference y . Therefore it is now very important to verify that the Meredith—Smith's result is actually explained by this effect and hence it is not a rule but an exception concerning the intensities of one or

two neighbouring bands in the spectrum rather than the spectrum on the whole.

Consider a ratio of the matrix elements of the functions (66),

$$Z \equiv \frac{\langle m | d_3(q) | n \rangle}{\langle m | d_2(q) | n \rangle}. \quad (67)$$

Its exact values calculated by numerical integration of the Schrödinger equation with the RKR potential can be found in figure 14 of paper [14]. The quasiclassical expression for Z will be obtained by writing down the matrix elements of the functions (66) with use of (30) and (23) as

$$\langle m | d_k(q) | n \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^k (d_{ki}/\alpha^i) \rho[x^i, y] \langle m | x | n \rangle, \quad (68)$$

where α is the Morse range parameter, $x = \alpha q$ and y is given by (20). Explicit expressions for $\rho[x^i, y]$ are given in Appendix. On inserting (68) into (67), the matrix element $\langle m | x | n \rangle$ containing the exponential factor is divided through and the ratio Z depends only upon the preexponential factors. As was indicated in § 2.2, these can be evaluated from the expressions derived for the Morse potential.

The following values of the HF spectroscopic parameters were taken from the handbook by Radtsig and Smirnov [122]: $\omega_e = 4139 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\omega_e x_e = 90 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B_e = 21 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $r_e = 0.9168 \text{ \AA}$. From here we find

$$\alpha = (\omega_e x_e / B_e)^{1/2} / r_e = 2.26 \text{ \AA}^{-1} \quad (69)$$

(this is identical with (65) where B is the parameter of the Birge—Sponer relation (64); B_e is the rotational constant*) and $x_e = 0.0217$. The coefficients of expansions (66) given in [14] for the Morse potential are $d_{21} = 1.5108$, $d_{22} = -0.3478$, $d_{31} = 1.5220$, $d_{32} = -0.2335$, $d_{33} = -1.0958$ (d_{ki} in units of $D/\text{\AA}^i$). Putting these values and equations (A4), (A5), (A14) and (A15) from Appendix into (68), we find the quasiclassical expression for the ratio (67),

$$Z = \frac{1.71 + 0.14\tau - 0.43\tau^2}{1 + 0.20\tau}, \quad (70)$$

where τ is given by (A12).

The calculated data are shown in table 2. The second column is exact ratios (67) of the matrix elements taken from figure 14 of paper [14] and the third one is their quasiclassical counterparts calculated by equation (70). It is seen that the quasiclassical function (70) indeed passes across zero near $n=6$ and then changes its sign. Consequently, the anomaly in the matrix elements discovered by Meredith and Smith is explained by the present theory as being due to vanishing the slowly varying preexponential factor. The agreement between the quasiclassical and exact values in table 2 should be considered as excellent taking into account that the absolute values of the matrix elements vary there by more than 4 orders of

* In equation (46) it was denoted by B but this should not lead to a confusion because these notations will no longer be used anywhere in what follows.

Table 2
The quasiclassical and the exact HF matrix element's ratios (67) explaining the origin of the Meredith-Smith anomaly

$m - n$	Z^*	Z^{**}
0-2	1,00	1,01
0-3	0,65	0,65
0-4	0,36	0,37
0-5	0,18	0,15
0-6	0,03***	-0,05
0-7	-0,10	-0,21
0-8	-0,15	-0,35
0-9	-0,24	-0,45
0-10	-0,36	-0,55

* From figure 14 of ref. [14].

** By equation (70).

*** In figure 14 (and in figures 7 and 17 as well) of reference [14], the matrix element $\langle 0|d_3(q)|6\rangle$ has an opposite sign and another absolute magnitude compared to the table of Appendix 2; when using its value from the table, here will be -0.001.

Note: 1,00 means 1.00.

be governed only by the potential function.

It is clear from the above that, given a certain representation of the dipole moment function, the anomalies under consideration can simply be discovered by calculating the functional ρ entering the preexponential factor (38). Often, instead of (66), the expansion of $d(q)$ is written as

$$d(q) = \sum_{l=0}^k M_l (q/r_e)^l, \quad (71)$$

where r_e is the equilibrium interatomic separation in Å and M_l are the expansion coefficients in Debye related to those of (66) through the equation

$$M_l = d_{kl} (r_e)^l. \quad (72)$$

Then it follows from definitions (23) and (32) that

$$\rho[V(x), y] = \sum_{l=1}^k \frac{M_l}{(ar_e)^l} \rho[x^l, y], \quad (73)$$

where a , as before, is the range parameter of the corresponding Morse curve.

Meredith and Smith [14] have calculated four sets of the coefficients d_{kl} for the HF molecule at $k=2$ and 3 taking the RKR or Morse potential

magnitude. It is remarkable that the extremely simple expression (70) reproduces so accurately the results of complicated computer calculations involving numerical integration of the Schrödinger equation with a numerical potential.

The results of the present and preceding sections convincingly demonstrate that the intensity distribution in the higher overtone spectrum are, as a rule, quite insensitive to the explicit form of the dipole moment function. The same conclusion has previously been drawn by Ferguson and Parkinson [100]. Nevertheless, possible occurrence of the Meredith-Smith anomaly in some systems should be kept in mind. If the dipole moment function is such that (32) vanishes for a certain $n \rightarrow m$ transition then this can be easily observed in experiment because of essential weakening or even absolute disappearance from the spectrum of the corresponding band. However, even in this case the intensity distribution of the other bands in the spectrum will again

for $\mathcal{E}(q)$ and using their experimental $n \leftarrow 0$ absorption data at $n \leq 3$ [12-14]. Sileo and Cool [11] have obtained the coefficients for HF and DF at $k=6$ using their emission data. The corresponding coefficients M_l calculated by means of equation (72) with r_e from [122] are given in the first 6 lines of table 3. Also displayed there are the values of M_l found from the overtone absorption spectra of some other molecules. Table 3 will be discussed in § 4.

Table 3
The expansion coefficients of the dipole moment function (71) in Debyes

Molecule	M_1	M_2	M_3	M_4	M_5	M_6	Remarks
HF [14]*	1,3837	-0,1994					(a)
	1,3851	-0,2923					(b)
	1,3962	-0,0677	-1,0848				(a)
	1,3954	-0,1963	-0,8444				(b)
HF [11]*	1,3954	-0,1182	-0,8523	-0,0556	0,0844	-0,4774	(c)
DF [11]*	1,3908	0,0461	-0,9817	-0,5857	0,1261	-0,1621	(c)
HCl [108]	1,2054	0,0384	-1,4882	-0,9881	-0,6476	-0,9358	(d)
HBr [21]	0,650	0,342	-1,669	-0,591	1,75		(d)
HI [102]	-0,0765	0,496	-1,94				(d)
[24]	-0,0734	0,5028	-1,9898	-0,1379	1,1467		(d)
CO [25]*	3,51	-0,19	-3,39				(a)
[26]*	3,50	-0,39	-3,27				(d)
[104]	3,54	-0,312	-3,46				(d)
[129]*	3,55	-0,32	-3,42				(a)
[103]*	3,5394	-0,3514	-3,644	2,307			(a)

* The values of d_{kl} from these papers were multiplied by $(r_e)^l$ according to (72) with r_e from [122].

(a) The RKR potential. (b) The Morse potential. (c) The RKR potential, data from the emission spectrum (other data from the absorption spectra). (d) The Dunham potential. Note: 1,3837 means 1.3837.

The values of the factor ρ from (73) were calculated by equations of Appendix using molecular constants from [122] and the parameters M_l from table 3. The results are shown in table 4. It is seen that the factor ρ goes across zero for all the molecules investigated. Namely, for HF it occurs near $n=6$, for HCl between $n=3$ and 4, for HBr between $n=2$ and 3, for HI between $n=1$ and 2, and for CO between $n=4$ and 5. Consequently, the Meredith-Smith anomaly should be present in the overtone absorption spectra of all the above molecules. A more detailed analysis of the experimental data on the absorption of diatomic molecules will be given in § 3.3.

Table 4

The values of the factor ρ calculated by virtue of equation (73) and of the equations given in Appendix with use of the coefficients M_i from table 3, and the experimental dipole moment matrix elements d_{mn} from the overtone absorption spectra with the signs defined theoretically (ρ and d_{mn} in Debye)

$m-n$	HF		HCl		HBr	
	$\rho^{(a)}$	d_{mn} [12-14]	ρ	d_{mn} [108]	ρ	d_{mn} [21] ^(b)
0-1	1,11	9,85-02	0,56	7,12-02	1,29	3,21-02 ^(j)
0-2	0,84	-1,25-02	0,42	-7,75-03	0,16	-2,69-03 ^(j)
0-3	0,57	1,63-03	0,16	5,15-04	-0,65*	-3,54-04*
0-4	0,34	-2,46-04 ⁽ⁱ⁾	-0,13*	-3,06-05	-1,10	2,19-04
0-5	0,14	3,34-05 ⁽ⁱ⁾	-0,37	-8,42-06*	-1,29	-7,61-05
0-6	-0,04*	4,52-08 ^{(i)*}	-0,56	6,61-06	-1,32	
0-7	-0,19	-3,50-06 ⁽ⁱ⁾	-0,69	-3,27-06 ⁽ⁱ⁾	-1,22	

$m-n$	HI		CO				
	$\rho^{(c)}$	d_{mn} [24] ^(d)	$\rho^{(e)}$	$\rho^{(f)}$	$\rho^{(g)}$	$\rho^{(h)}$	d_{mn} [103]
0-1	0,69	-3,98-03*	2,11	2,12	2,16	2,25	1,055-01
0-2	-0,14*	1,78-03	1,45	1,52	1,51	1,88	-6,57-03
0-3	-0,81	-1,11-03	0,82	0,93	0,88	1,11	4,24-04
0-4	-1,29	3,95-04	0,27	0,42	0,32	0,27	-2,011-05
0-5	-1,61	-1,36-04	-0,22*	-0,04*	-0,16*	-0,57*	1,275-06 ^(k)
0-6	-1,82		-0,65	-0,44	-0,60	-1,37	
0-7	-1,96		-1,04	-0,81	-0,99	-2,14	

^(a) The coefficients M_i from the fourth line of table 3. ^(b) The signs are given in the right-hand sides of the equations in table 6. ^(c) The coefficients M_i from the tenth line of table 3; with those from the ninth line, the similar values are obtained. ^(d) The signs are given in the right-hand sides of the equations in table 4. ^(e) - ^(h) The coefficients M_i from references [25, 26, 104, 103] respectively (see table 3); the coefficients from [129] give much about the same as those from [104]. ⁽ⁱ⁾ The values calculated by Meredith and Smith [14] showing an anomaly at level 6 (see their table in Appendix 2 where similar anomalies are present at the $8 \rightleftharpoons 1$ and $9 \rightleftharpoons 2$ transitions). ^(j) Average values. ^(k) The Chackerian's theoretical value obtained by a simple extrapolation; in view of the anomaly expected at the fifth level, the matrix element d_{05} should be much lower in absolute magnitude and have the opposite sign (see text). ^(l) From reference [18], the sign was added by us. * The changes in both the sign of ρ and the succession of the sign alternation of the matrix elements d_{mn} simultaneously indicate the Meredith-Smith anomaly (see text). Note: 1,11 means 1.11.

Burberry and Albrecht [40] have computed the coefficients d_{21} and d_{22} of the expansion (66) for the local CH and CD vibrations in benzene and its deuterium substituted derivatives using, as the potential, the Morse

function or the quartic polynomial. For the Morse function they have found $d_{22}/d_{21} < 0$, and taking into account that $\rho[x^2, y] < 0$ (see figure 1) one could infer that the anomaly is absent since (73) does not vanish. However, it may emerge when account will be taken of the succeeding terms in expansion (66). The results of paper [40] are not included in table 3 by the reasons noted in § 4.

To estimate a possible error in determining the anomaly position, the factors ρ were calculated for all 6 sets of coefficients M_i available in table 3 for HF and DF. As was the case for the CH vibrations, the quadratic expansions of $d(q)$ (the first two lines in table 3) turn out to be insufficient for revealing the anomaly. With the coefficients of the third line, the anomaly for HF arises between the levels $n=4$ and 5, with those of the fourth near $n=6$, of the fifth near $n=5$ and of the sixth for DF between $n=3$ and 4. Thus, when taking the expansions of $d(q)$ of power $k \geq 3$, equation (73) quite unambiguously predicts the positions of two anomalous bands in the HF overtone absorption spectrum within the interval $n=4-7$.

It is appropriate to point out a simple way of finding the Meredith-Smith anomaly based on the signs of the matrix elements, which are fixed by a proper choice of the signs of the vibrational wave functions. In the present work, the signs are chosen in such a way that the wave functions are positive at $q \rightarrow +\infty$ (for the Morse potential, this corresponds to the conventional representation of the wave functions with use of the Laguerre polynomials). Such a sign convention is commonly accepted in a majority of contemporary works.

As is seen from equation (29), the matrix elements of the linear dipole moment function are strictly alternating in the signs. For example, at $m=0$ and $n=1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$ we have the following sign series: (+ - + - + ...). According to (30), just the same sign alternation should take place for an arbitrary dipole moment function $V(x)$ provided that $\rho[V(x), y]$ does not vanish anywhere. For this reason, the anomaly can easily be discovered through the breakdown of this regularity in the sign alternation (the existence of regularities in signs of matrix elements has been previously pointed out by Cashion [109] and Ferguson and Parkinson [100]).

Experimentally measured are only absolute values of the dipole moment matrix elements, but there are a number of indirect means for determining their relative signs [13, 21, 24, 104, 108]. Table 4 summarizes the experimental dipole moment matrix elements for the diatomic molecules extracted from the overtone absorption spectra along with their signs defined theoretically. The HF experimental absorption spectrum provides the matrix elements with $n < 3$ only; shown in table 4 at $n \geq 4$ are the numerical data calculated by Meredith and Smith [14] with the coefficients M_i from the third line of table 3. It is seen that the regular sign alternation breaks once at $n=6$, i. e. just at the same level near which ρ crosses zero*. The similar

* Meredith and Smith [14] have calculated d_{mn} at all the quantum numbers $m < n < 10$. Their table in Appendix 2 displays the sign anomalies at $m=1, n=8$ and $m=2, n=9$ as well. However, such anomalies are not seen in Sileo and Cool's [11] tables 6 and 7 for HF and DF, except for an evident misprint in table 6 where the matrix element $5 \rightleftharpoons 1$ is wrong in its sign.

effect is observed for other molecules as well: for HCl the sign alternation breaks at $n=5$, for HBr at $n=3$, for HI at $n=1$ (just the first matrix element d_{01} has a "wrong" sign). For CO experiments have been performed at $n \leq 4$ only but the anomaly is expected at $n=5$, so that the CO sign succession is not violated. Thus the Meredith—Smith anomaly can be revealed through both zero of the factor ρ and the violation of the regular sign alternation in the matrix elements so far as, resulting from the present theory and being confirmed by table 4, both these events occur simultaneously at the same level n .

Chackerian [103] has made an attempt to predict the CO $5 \leftarrow 0$ band intensity. He has noticed that the experimental points at $n \leq 4$ are well fitted by a straight line on the plot of $\log d_{0n}$ vs. n and, having this line prolonged up to the $5 \leftarrow 0$ transition region, he has obtained the value shown in table 4. Then, giving d_{05} the " \pm " signs in turn, he has calculated the expansion coefficients of $d(q)$ up to q^5 inclusive. It has appeared that at $d_{05} < 0$ the function $d(q)$ decreased at large q whereas it rised if $d_{05} > 0$, i. e. the more reasonable choice, as writes Chackerian, is $d_{05} < 0$. However, in the latter case the vibration-rotation interaction would lead, on his opinion, "to an enhancement of the P branch over the R branch, a result which would be somewhat surprising since the opposite effect is observed in all the lower overtones". Therefore $d_{05} > 0$ was chosen. In contrast to this, our results show that d_{05} should be negative and anomalously low, much lower than the value given by Chackerian. It is surprising why he did not calculated this matrix element directly using the expansion coefficients M_i found by him up to $i=4$.

We also made an attempt to calculate the CO $5 \leftarrow 0$ band intensity using the values of the factor ρ from table 4 but such kind of predictions proved to be of too low confidence by the reasons noted at the end of § 3.3.

3. COMPARISON OF THE THEORY WITH EXPERIMENT

A number of data on band intensities in overtone absorption and emission spectra of diatomic and polyatomic molecules are available in literature enabling the theoretical predictions to be compared with the experimental findings. For the $n \leftarrow 0$ overtone absorption the theory predicts the normal band intensity distribution law (45) and the deuterium isotope effect (54) as well as the occurrence of the Meredith—Smith anomalies. For the overtone emission spectra the predictions are as follows.

1. The intensity ratio of two transitions $n \rightarrow m_1$ and $n \rightarrow m_2$ starting at a common upper level n is independent of n , being a function of m_1 and m_2 only (equation (39)).

2. If the level m_1 is far enough from the ground state, then the relative intensity distribution obeys equation (49) where μ_{m_1} is the vibrational energy in units of $\hbar\omega$ (see definition (20)) and λ is expressed in terms of the molecular parameters by equation (46).

3. If both the lower levels m_1 and m_2 are high enough above the ground state, then the relative intensities are distributed according to equation (50).

3.1. Overtone absorption spectra of the local CH(CD) stretching vibrations in polyatomic molecules

The $n \leftarrow 0$ overtone absorption band intensities for the CT and CD vibrations in benzene and its deuterium substituted derivatives have been measured in [37—47]. Figure 2 shows the data by Burberry and Albrecht [40] and Reddy et al. [47]. The abscissa is the square root of the energy of the upper level n divided by a quantum of harmonic frequency, $\hbar\omega$, and the ordinate is the logarithm to the base ten of the $n \leftarrow 0$ transition oscillator strength per one local CH or CD stretching vibration (for clarity of the figure, the CD ordinate origin was shifted upwards by two units).

Fig. 2. The experimental distributions of the oscillator strengths f_{0n} per one local vibration in the CH (left ordinate) and CD (right ordinate) overtone absorption spectra of C_6H_6 , C_6H_5D , $C_6H_4D_2$ and C_6D_6 versus square root of the upper level energy in $\hbar\omega$ units. ●: liquid phase, data from [40]; X: gas phase, data from table 4 of [47]; ⊗: data from figure 9 of [47] (see text). The straight lines are least squares fits. 1: CH, the slope is $a = 4.67$, the standard deviation is $\Delta a = 0.09$ (one $n=6$ point (●) with the largest deviation shown in the figure is omitted in calculating a and Δ); 2: CD, $a = 5.04$, $\Delta = 0.28$

Reddy et al. [47] write in the caption for figure 9 that the CD experimental intensities at $n=2-4$ given in their table 4 are probably in excess by about 3 times because of suspected but unknown systematic errors, so they give in figure 9 the assumed rather than measured values. In our figure 2 all the data from their table 4, as well as 3 additional points $n=2, 3, 4$ from their figure 9 are shown.

As is seen from figure 2, the experimental data satisfy the theoretical relationship (45), being well laid on the straight lines which are linear least squares fits

$$\lg f_{0n} = \text{const} - a\sqrt{\mu_n} \quad (74)$$

The slope of line 1 for CH is $a = 4.67$ and that of line 2 for CD is $a = 5.04$. The root-mean-square deviations of the experimental points from these lines are 0,09 and 0,28 respectively. The scatter of the points for CD is much large than that for CH, still being within the experimental uncertainties. In calculating the parameters of line 2 for CD, all points plotted in figure 2 were taken into account. In the case of line 1 for CH, one point (●) at $n=6$ with the largest deviation was omitted; if it is included in the

calculation, the result is $a=4.73$ and $\Delta=0.18$. Given the standard deviation Δ , the uncertainty δa in the slope is easily obtained from the equation

$$\delta a = \Delta / (x_{\max} - x_{\min}), \quad (75)$$

where x_{\max} and x_{\min} are the maximum and minimum values of abscissae of experimental points. Considering that $\beta \sim 1/a$ we get the following equation for the uncertainty $\delta\beta$ in the potential range parameter β :

$$\delta\beta = (\beta/a)\delta a. \quad (76)$$

According to (54), where $\lambda = a \ln 10$, the ratio of the slopes for CD and CH should be equal to

$$\left(\frac{a_D}{a_H}\right)_{\text{teop}} = \left(\frac{M_{CD}}{M_{CH}}\right)^{1/4} = 1.17. \quad (77)$$

Actually, the above data result in the ratio

$$(a_D/a_H)_{\text{exp. CH}} = 1.08. \quad (78)$$

Here it is difficult to speak of a numerical agreement between (77) and (78) because of a too high scatter of the CD experimental points. Nevertheless it may definitely be asserted that the experiment confirms the predicted slight increase in the slope on deuteration.

Full circles and crosses in figure 3 show the relative oscillator strengths for the CH vibrations in benzene measured by Patel et al. [42] and Yamamoto et al. [46] respectively. They are well fitted by the

Fig. 3. The experimental relative oscillator strengths in the overtone absorption spectra of the local CH vibrations in polyatomic molecules versus square root of the upper state energy in $\hbar\omega$ units.

● and ×: liquid phase benzene, data from [42] and [46] respectively (left ordinate); ○: averaged data [41, 55] (right ordinate) for the CH vibrations in aromatic and aliphatic groups in 10 polyatomic molecules (benzene, toluene, xylene, tetramethylsilane, hexane etc.). The straight lines are least squares fits. 1: $a=4.79$, $\Delta=0.10$ (two last crosses with large deviations shown in the figure were not included in the calculation); 2: $a=4.79$, $\Delta=0.01$

straight line 1 drawn with no account of two last crosses ($n=8, 9$) having the highest deviations from the line. Its parameters are $a=4.79$, $\Delta=0.10$. When the $n=8$ point (×) is added, there will be $a=4.68$, $\Delta=0.17$.

Burberry et al. [41, 55] have noticed a universality of the experimental overtone absorption intensities in large polyatomic molecules and they have derived the average intensity values of the data for the CH vibrations

belonging to 6 aromatic and 8 aliphatic groups in 10 different alkanes and methyl substituted benzenes. Their averaged relative intensities are shown by open circles in figure 3. They are fitted by the straight line 2 with the slope $a=4.79$ and the standard deviation $\Delta=0.01$. Thus the data of figures 2 and 3 give

$$a = 4.73 \pm 0.06. \quad (79)$$

The slope a being known, one can calculate the parameter β describing the potential of the local CH vibration at large negative displacements (see definition (43)). Recast equation (46) in the form

$$\beta = 10.51 (\bar{M}\bar{\omega})^{1/2}/a, \quad (80)$$

where \bar{M} is the reduced mass in atomic units, $\bar{\omega}$ is the harmonic frequency in units of 10^3 cm^{-1} ($\bar{\omega} = \omega_e \cdot 10^{-3}$) and β is in \AA^{-1} . Then, putting here the parameters of the CH vibrations ($\bar{M}=0.930$ [122], $\bar{\omega}=3.157$ [47]) and a from (79), we get $\beta = (3.81 \pm 0.05) \text{\AA}^{-1}$.

Fang and Swofford [58] have measured the overtone absorption of halomethanes CHX_3 and CH_2X_2 ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$) in liquid phase. Their data are shown in figure 4. The common logarithm of the ratio of the oscillator strength for the $n \leftarrow 0$ transition to its value for the $3 \leftarrow 0$ transition is plotted on the ordinate axis, the abscissa being the same as in figures 2 and 3. The experimental points for CH_2X_2 are on the straight line 1 with the slope $a=4.80$ and the standard deviation $\Delta=0.05$ ($\delta a=0.07$ by equation (75)) and those for CHX_3 are on line 2 with $a=5.80$ and $\Delta=0.08$ ($\delta a=0.11$). Using these values, we get from (76) and (80) $\beta = (3.76 \pm 0.07) \text{\AA}^{-1}$ for CH_2X_2 and $\beta = (3.10 \pm 0.05) \text{\AA}^{-1}$ for CHX_3 (\bar{M} and $\bar{\omega}$ are taken the same as for benzene).

Fig. 4. The experimental relative oscillator strengths in the CH vibration overtone absorption spectra of liquid phase halomethanes [58] versus square root of the upper level energy in $\hbar\omega$ units. ●: CHCl_3 , ×: CHBr_3 , ○: CH_2Cl_2 , +: CH_2Br_2 . The straight lines are least squares fits. 1: $a=4.80$, $\Delta=0.05$; 2: $a=5.80$, $\Delta=0.08$

These results imply that the CH bond potential is insensitive to the sort of the atom X replacing the hydrogen ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br) but it depends on the total number of the CH bonds retained; namely, the slope appreciably decreases from CHX_3 to CH_2X_2 , being for the latter almost the same as that for benzene and other large molecules. Hence it should be expected for the slope to keep constant in going from CH_2X_2 to CH_3X .

3.2. Overtone emission spectra of diatomic molecules

Sileo and Cool [11] have measured the relative intensities of the HF and DF $n \rightarrow m$ overtone emission at $n-m \leq 6$ from the HF levels $n \leq 9$ and from the DF levels $n \leq 12$. The experimental results along with the overtone absorption data by Meredith et al. [12-14] have been presented as the tables of the relative dipole moment matrix elements squared which may actually be identified with the relative oscillator strengths. Thus from the tables we obtain the ratios $f_{m_1 n} / f_{m_2 n}$ for the transitions $n \rightarrow m_1$ and $n \rightarrow m_2$ from the same upper level n to two lower levels $m_1 > m_2 \geq 0$.

The tables [11] contain 26 experimental points for HF and 37 points for DF, but only for the transitions to neighbouring levels, i. e. $m_2 = m_1 - 1$. However these data can easily be recalculated using the recurrence relation

$$f_{m_1 n} / f_{m_2 - 1, n} = (f_{m_1 n} / f_{m_2 n}) (f_{m_2 n} / f_{m_2 - 1, n}). \quad (81)$$

Fig. 5. The experimental intensity distributions in the HF (●, the bottom abscissa) and DF (+, the top abscissa) overtone emission spectra.

Data from [11] (see text) with $m_2 \geq 2$. The abscissa is the difference between square roots of the energies of two lower states m_1 and m_2 , the ordinate is common logarithm of the intensity ratio for the transitions $n \rightarrow m_1$ and $n \rightarrow m_2$ from the same upper level n . The straight lines are least squares fits drawn through the coordinate origin. 1: $a=6.76$, $\Delta=0.23$; 2: $a=7.92$, $\Delta=0.39$

to give the relative oscillator strengths at other values of $m_2 < m_1 - 1$. In fact, at $m_2 = m_1 - 1$ both the multipliers in the right-hand side are known from the experimental tables and at $m_2 < m_1 - 1$ the first multiplier is known from the previous calculation, the second one being taken from the tables. In such a way, 63 experimental points for HF and 94 ones for DF were obtained. They all are plotted in figures 5 and 6 (downstairs right with the bottom abscissa is for HF, upstairs left with the top abscissa is for DF, the DF abscissa origins in figures 5 and 6 being displaced to the left by 0.5 and 1 unit respectively). The ordinates are common logarithms of the ratios of the matrix elements squared for the transitions from one upper level n to two different levels $m_1 > m_2$. The abscissa in figure 5 is the difference of the square roots of the lower state energies in units of $\hbar\omega$ and that in figure 6 is the square root of the m_1 level energy in the same units.

Fig. 6. The experimental intensity distributions in the HF (the bottom abscissa) and DF (the top abscissa) overtone emission spectra.

Data from [11] (see text) with $m_2=0$ (●) and $m_2=1$ (+). The abscissa is square root of the m_1 level energy in $\hbar\omega$ units, the ordinate is the same as in figure 5. The straight lines are least squares fits. 1: $a=6.52$, $\Delta=0.10$; 2: $a=6.42$, $\Delta=0.08$; 3: $a=7.29$, $\Delta=0.22$; 4: $a=7.08$, $\Delta=0.07$. In calculating the slopes a and the standard deviations Δ for lines 2 and 4 ($m_2=0$), the points with the least abscissae corresponding to $m_1=1$ were omitted (see text)

Groups of points arranged vertically are seen in these figures. Within each group m_1 and m_2 are fixed and only n varies. To check the first prediction of the theory given at the beginning of § 3, i. e. that the oscillator strength ratios are independent of n , average values and standard deviations of $\log(f_{m_1 n} / f_{m_2 n})$ were calculated for each group of two or more points. The results shown in table 5 unequivocally confirm the above prediction. Indeed, the HF relative oscillator strengths vary all over the table by about several orders of magnitude whereas their largest variations within a group with m_1 and m_2 fixed are given by a factor of 1.7. Actually, these variations are much lower for many groups. For example, at $m=0$ and m_1 varying from 1 to 4 the deviations from the average values at each m_1 are not more than 20%, the averages themselves varying by almost 5 orders of magnitude. For DF this rule is worse fulfilled, however the deviations from the averages generally do not exceed the experimental errors. Only at large $n=8, 9$ they become too high but in this case the energy difference $\epsilon_n - \epsilon_{m_1}$ is quite small and, probably, the theory is no longer valid.

To check the other predictions of the theory, all the experimental data were divided in two groups. The first group included the points with $m_2 \geq 2$ and the $m_2=2$ level was supposed to be high enough for applying equation (50). Figure 5 shows a plot of the experimental data vs. the difference of square roots of the dimensionless energies. The linear least squares fits 1 and 2 for HF and DF respectively were drawn through the coordinate origin. The slope of line 1 is $a=6.76$, the standard deviation of the experimental points being $\Delta=0.23$ (equation (75) with $x_{m_1 n}=0$ then gives $\delta a=0.28$); the parameters of line 2 are $a=7.92$ and $\Delta=0.39$ ($\delta a=0.43$). Thus the relation (50) is well supported by the HF experimental

Table 5

Average values and standard deviations of common logarithms of the relative oscillator strengths, $\log(f_{m_1n}/f_{m_2n})$, in the HF and DF overtone emission spectra [11] exhibiting a weak dependence upon n at fixed m_1 and m_2

m_2	m_1	HF	DF	m_2	m_1	HF	DF	
0	1	2,06±0,06	2,29±0,16	4	5	1,28±0,13	1,57±0,20	
	2	3,82±0,08	4,31±0,11		6	2,64±0,17	3,07±0,25	
	3	5,42±0,05			7		4,45±0,22	
	4	6,88±0,08			8		5,71±0,04	
1	2	1,74±0,06	1,94±0,21	5	6	1,28±0,23	1,45±0,19	
	3	3,33±0,11	3,77±0,27		7		2,91±0,20	
	4	4,80±0,09	5,48±0,22		8		4,28±0,01	
2	3	1,57±0,10	1,75±0,19	6	7		1,39±0,13	
	4	3,05±0,08	3,46±0,31		8		2,83±0,18	
	5	4,34±0,11	5,08±0,26		7	8		1,37±0,20
	6	5,63±0,14	6,50±0,12			9		2,71±0,31
3	4	1,45±0,10	1,62±0,18	8	9		1,22±0,41	
	5	2,78±0,07	3,23±0,30		10		1,35±0,58	
	6	4,09±0,19	4,74±0,21					
	7		6,03±0,05					

Note: 2,06 means 2.06.

data; the linear fit to the DF data is not so good but the deviations of the points from the straight line are still reasonable.

The ratio of two slopes results in the deuterium substitution effect

$$(a_D/a_H)_{\text{exp. HF}} = 1.17 \pm 0.11, \quad (82)$$

which is to be compared with the theoretical value (77) identical for CH and HF. While the numerical coincidence between the theory and the experiment should be considered as moderate because of a large data scatter, a slight increase in the slope upon deuteration predicted by the theory is clearly supported by the experiment.

Further turn to figure 6 showing the experimental data for small values of $m_2=0$ and 1 when equation (50) does not hold. However, equation (49) must yet be valid at large m_1 . As is clear from the above, considered here as "large" are the quantum numbers $m \geq 2$. Therefore the straight lines 2 and 4 in figure 6 are drawn with no account of groups of the points corresponding to $m_1=1$ (i. e. of those with the least abscissae). As the same parameter λ enters (49) and (50), the line slopes in figures 5 and 6 should be the same as well. In fact, figure 6 yields $a=6.52$, $\Delta=0.10$, $\delta a=0.12$ (line 1) and $a=6.42$, $\Delta=0.08$, $\delta a=0.08$ (line 2) for HF and $a=7.29$, $\Delta=0.22$, $\delta a=0.19$ (line 3) and $a=7.08$, $\Delta=0.07$, $\delta a=0.14$ (line 4) for DF. Discrepancies with the results of figure 5, which are especially large for

DF, are seen here. The data in figure 5 are of higher confidence due to better statistics, so for the slope one has $a=6.76 \pm 0.30$. Inserting this value along with the HF parameters ($\bar{M}=0.957$, $\bar{\omega}=4.139$ [122]) into (80) yields $\beta=(3.09 \pm 0.14) \text{ \AA}^{-1}$.

Overtone emission intensities of hydroxyl radical OH were reported in [1–9]. The most extensive data were obtained by Krassovskiy et al. [4] (see also [123, 124]) from the airglow spectrum of the night sky and by Garvin et al. [5, 6] from the spectrum of the H+O₃ atomic flame. Krassovskiy's data are shown in figures 7 and 8, being handled just as those for HF. Here again vertical groups of points with different n but fixed m_1 and m_2 are seen. It is obvious that the relative intensities depend only slightly upon n at given m_1 and m_2 , just as predicted by equation (39). The line in figure 7 has the slope $a=5.54 \pm 0.33$ (lines 1 and 2 in figure 8 have $a=5.88 \pm 0.31$ and $a=5.62 \pm 0.48$ respectively). Putting this value and the OH parameters ($\bar{M}=0.948$, $\bar{\omega}=3.735$ [122]) into (80) yields $\beta=(3.57 \pm 0.22) \text{ \AA}^{-1}$.

The data by Garvin et al. [6] were also processed giving the slope $a=5.57 \pm 0.70$. Here is a very large scatter of the experimental points. However Ferguson and Parkinson [100] have pointed out that the $n-m_1=2$ transition intensities in table 3 by Garvin et al. [6] were too low by about a factor of ten, which is additionally confirmed by more recent airglow hydroxyl intensity measurements [2]. Moreover, this table displays a value of 810 (in arbitrary units) for the $6 \rightarrow 2$ transition intensity whereas table 2 by Garvin [5] gives 8.1 for this quantity when recalculated with use

Fig. 7. The experimental intensity distribution in the OH overtone emission spectrum. Data from [4] with $m_2 \geq 2$. The axes are the same as in figure 5. The straight line is a least squares fit with the slope $a=5.54$ and the standard deviation of the experimental points $\Delta=0.22$.

Fig. 8. The experimental intensity distribution in the OH overtone emission spectrum. Data from [4] with $m_2=0$ (●) and $m_2=1$ (×). The axes are the same as in figure 6. The straight lines are least squares fits: 1: $a=5.88$, $\Delta=0.14$; 2: $a=5.62$, $\Delta=0.12$. Line 2 is drawn without taking into account the points with the least abscissae corresponding to $m_1=1$.

of the author's normalization; it is the latter figure that seems to be right. These corrections being made, the point scatter is greatly reduced and Garvin's data conform on the whole to Krassovsky's ones.

3.3. Overtone absorption spectra of diatomic molecules

The HCl overtone absorption band intensities were measured in [15—18] (see also [108]). The results are shown in table 4 and in figure 9 where the abscissa is square root of the upper level energy in units of $\hbar\omega$ and the ordinate is common logarithm of the dipole moment matrix element squared. In accordance with the results of §2.6 (see table 4), here is the Meredith—Smith anomaly resulting in weakening the intensities of the transitions to levels 4 and 5. Reddy [17] has qualified as surprising the fact that the intensities of the $5 \leftarrow 0$ and $6 \leftarrow 0$ bands measured by him were very close to one another, although the $6 \leftarrow 0$ band intensity should be expected to be much lower. Now it finds a natural explanation. Namely, the $6 \leftarrow 0$ band intensity is a normal one and that of the $5 \leftarrow 0$ band is anomalously low. Moreover, a possibility can not be disregarded that in some molecules the $n+1 \leftarrow 0$ transition will be more intensive at some value of n than the $n \leftarrow 0$ one providing the factor ρ (see § 2.6, equation

Fig. 9. The experimental dipole moment matrix elements squared from the HCl overtone absorption spectrum [15—18].

The abscissa is square root of the upper state energy in $\hbar\omega$ units, the ordinate is common logarithm of the dipole moment matrix element squared (d_{0n} in Debye). There are the anomalous bands with low intensities at $n=4$ and 5. The straight line is a least squares fit to the experimental points except the anomalous ones. The slope is $a=6.65$, the standard deviation is $\Delta=0.21$

(73)) crosses zero closely enough to the level n , as is the case, e. g., for HF at $n=6$ (see table 4). The straight line in figure 9 is drawn by the least squares method ignoring two anomalous points. Its slope is $a=6.65$, the root-mean-square deviation of the experimental points being $\Delta=0.21$. Estimating an uncertainty in the slope by equation (75) yields $a=6.65 \pm 0.16$.

Intensities of the HBr and HI overtone absorption bands have been reported in papers [19—21, 125, 126] and [22—24, 127] respectively. They are plotted in figure 10. The HBr anomaly is at level $n=3$, those for HI are at levels $n=1$ and 2 in perfect accordance with the predictions of table 4.

The line slopes in figure 10 are $a=5.06 \pm 0.21$ for HBr and $a=4.34 \pm 0.10$ for HI.

The parameter β for the repulsive branch of the potential is now calculated from the slopes. Inserting the above values of a and the molecular constants from [122] ($\bar{M}=0.98, 0.995, 1.0$ and $\bar{\omega}=2.991, 2.649, 2.308$ for HCl, HBr and HI respectively) into (80) yields $\beta=(2.71 \pm 0.06) \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ for HCl, $\beta=(3.37 \pm 0.14) \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ for HBr and $\beta=(3.68 \pm 0.08) \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ for HI. The uncertainties in the a and β values were calculated by equations (75) and (76) using the standard deviations Δ of the experimental points from the straight lines.

Fig. 10. The experimental dipole moment matrix elements squared (d_{0n} in Debye) from the HBr [21] (left panel) and HI [24] (right panel) overtone absorption spectra.

The axes are the same as in figure 9. There are the anomalously weak bands $n=3$ (HBr) and $n=1, 2$ (HI). The straight lines are least squares fits to the experimental points excluding the anomalous bands. For HBr, $a=5.06$, $\Delta=0.21$; for HI, $a=4.34$, $\Delta=0.04$

The straight line is drawn letting the $n=1$ points aside. Its slope is $a=9.37 \pm 0.27$, whence $\beta=(4.33 \pm 0.13) \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ ($\bar{M}=6.86$, $\bar{\omega}=2.170$ [122]).

In view of the fact that the results of table 4 predict the CO anomaly at $n=4-5$, it would be interesting to estimate the anomalous band intensities using the normal intensity distribution from figure 11 and the factors ρ from table 4. Such a calculation was first performed for HCl, HBr and HI since both the positions and the intensities of the anomalous bands are known for these molecules along with more accurate normal distributions. Unfortunately, the predicted values proved to be at variance with the experimental ones by a factor of $10^{\pm 1.5}$, making the predicted anomalous band intensities extremely uncertain. The reason lies in both a high sensitivity of the factor ρ near the anomaly to the explicit form of the dipole moment function $d(q)$ and a low accuracy of the quasiclassical approximation in a close vicinity of the anomaly (see footnote for table 1). It was seen in § 2.6 that different sets of the HF coefficients M_i from table 3 resulted in even different positions of two anomalous bands within $n=4-7$, and the absolute values of the factor ρ near its zero are affected to a still greater extent. Table 4 contains the factors ρ calculated with the sets of the CO coefficients M_i from table 3. They all predict the anomaly at

levels 4 and 5. However, while far away from the anomaly ρ is nearly insensitive to the form of $d(q)$, at the anomaly it is strongly affected even by the relatively weak changes in M_i (note that the intensity is proportional to ρ^2). But on the other hand this implies that the function $d(q)$

Fig. 11. The experimental dipole moment matrix elements squared (d_{0n} in Debye) from the CO overtone absorption spectrum [25–27]. The axes are the same as in figure 9. The straight line is a least squares fit to the experimental points with $n=2, 3, 4$; it has $a=9.37$ and $\Delta=0.14$. In view of the anomaly predicted by the theory (see text), the experimental point (still not measured) at abscissa 2.31 corresponding to the $5 \rightarrow 0$ band is expected to be situated far below the straight line

can be reconstructed with a higher accuracy when using the intensities of only the anomalous bands instead of those of all the bands in the spectrum.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The following conclusions can be drawn from the material presented.

1. The intensity distribution in the overtone spectrum is governed by the potential function $\mathcal{E}(q)$ at large negative displacements q from the equilibrium position where it exceeds the dissociation energy D .

2. The dipole moment function $d(q)$ enters only the preexponential factor ρ , which is an universal function for $d(q)$ given and depends only slightly on the energy difference y (in units of a harmonic frequency quantum) between two vibrational states involved. Therefore the intensity distribution in the higher overtone spectrum is in general insensitive to the form of $d(q)$ and cannot be used to determine $d(q)$ with a high precision far away from the equilibrium.

3. The only exception of this rule is the Meredith—Smith anomaly, which occurs, as was shown in § 2.6, when the slow function ρ passes across zero and then changes its sign at some value of y . The anomaly results in lowering the intensity of the corresponding band (or two adjacent bands). The anomalous band intensities are strongly affected by the form of $d(q)$ and therefore they perhaps could be used for determining $d(q)$.

4. Away from the equilibrium, the potential $\mathcal{E}(q)$ can be approximated by the simple exponential function (43) where β is a new molecular parameter characteristic of the potential behavior at $q < 0$ and $\mathcal{E}(q) > D$.

5. The normal intensity distribution law for the overtone spectra is derived, which is represented by a straight line on the plot of intensity

logarithm vs. square root of the upper level energy measured from the potential minimum and divided by the harmonic frequency quantum. The slope of this line is given by equation (46) in terms of the conventional constants and one unknown parameter β .

6. Analysis of the experimental data based on equations (45), (49) and (50) confirms the occurrence of the normal intensity distributions in the overtone spectra of all the diatomic systems investigated, for which the values of the parameter β were obtained. They are summarized in table 6.

Table 6
Slopes of the straight lines describing the normal intensity distributions in the vibration overtone spectra and the parameters for diatomic potentials

Diatomic system	a	α^* , \AA^{-1}	β , \AA^{-1}	Remarks
CH	4.73	1.77	$3.81 \pm 0.05^{(a)}$	LM ^(b) in benzene
	4.80		3.76 ± 0.07	LM in CH_2X_2 ^(c)
	5.80		3.10 ± 0.05	LM in CHX_3 ^(c)
OH	5.54	2.16	3.57 ± 0.22	(A)
HF	6.76	2.26	3.09 ± 0.14	(A)
HCl	6.65	1.75	2.71 ± 0.06	
HBr	5.06	1.63	3.37 ± 0.14	
HI	4.34	1.52	3.68 ± 0.08	
CO	9.37	2.33	4.33 ± 0.13	

* The Morse parameter by formulae (65) and (69). ^(a) Statistical errors; by definition (43), here β is twice as low as compared to [122]. ^(b) Local modes. ^(c) X=Cl, Br. ^(d) From the overtone emission spectra (the rest of data is from the absorption spectra). Note: 4.73 means 4.73.

7. Equation (54) explains the weak deuterium substitution effect observed experimentally for the local CH vibrations in benzene and for the HF molecule. Also, it predicts a much faster decrease in higher overtone intensities for the diatomic systems with no light atoms (H or D), which is confirmed by the CO experimental data.

8. The Meredith—Smith anomalies are proved to occur in the HCl, HBr and HI overtone absorption spectra. An anomalous decrease in intensity is predicted for the CO $5 \rightarrow 0$ absorption band.

Of great importance is the question what kind of information on a diatomic system is contained in its vibrational spectra. The probabilities of the $n \leftarrow m$ transitions with small vibrational energy changes, which govern the fundamental and low overtone band intensities, depend on the forms of $\mathcal{E}(q)$ and $d(q)$ near the equilibrium. The potential being well-known in this range, it is natural to expand $d(q)$ in powers of q and then to calculate the expansion coefficients using the experimental data.

Applying this method to higher overtone spectra has met serious difficulties. Sileo and Cool [11] found out that the numerical results by Meredith and Smith [14] correlated well with the HF experimental data at

$\Delta v \leq 3$ ($\Delta v = n - m$, in our notations) but large discrepancies arose at $\Delta v = 4-6$. In such cases it is usually inferred that $d(q)$ should be expanded to higher powers of q . Sileo and Cool used the expansions up to q^8 and obtained that the discrepancies between the theory and experiment were not further decreasing when rising the power beyond six, while they had in their disposition 26 linear equations in only 8 unknowns. Burberry and Albrecht [40] also suggested that higher order terms in the $d(q)$ expansion are to be used when calculating higher overtone intensities for the benzene CH vibrations, the reference being made to the Meredith-Smith's result [14] that adding a cubic term greatly affects the calculated transition intensities. Moreover, Meredith and Smith compared the results for the Morse and RKR potentials and did not observe significant differences (see below). These were just the reasons to conclude that $d(q)$ affects the intensities more strongly than $\mathcal{E}(q)$.

The second difficulty is that the $d(q)$ expansion coefficients calculated from the higher overtone spectra are changing when deuterium is substituted for hydrogen. For example, Burberry and Albrecht [40] obtained for the benzene local CH vibrations that the second coefficient M_2 changed by a factor of two and Sileo and Cool [11] obtained for HF that M_2 changed about three times, M_4 ten times and M_6 three times (see table 3). These results suggest the theory to be not self-consistent because the statical molecular properties, such as the coefficients M_i , should not be affected by changing its dynamics. Burberry and Albrecht hope to overcome this difficulty by using higher order terms in the $d(q)$ expansion or, perhaps, absolutely different representations of the dipole moment function, however such an approach give little chance as results from the Sileo and Cool's findings.

On the other hand, Ferguson and Parkinson [100] put forward just an opposite point of view concerning the role played by the dipole moment. These authors computed the matrix elements of the power functions $d(q) = q^k$ ($k=1, \dots, 5$) and the exponential functions $d(q) = \text{rexp}(-cr)$ (r stands for the interatomic distance) at three different values of c for the OH radical. They found the relative matrix elements $d_{mn}/d_{m'n}$ for higher overtones to be very similar for the different functions $d(q)$ whence the conclusion was drawn that the experimental higher overtone relative intensities did not enable one to reconstruct the dipole moment function and that it would be sufficient to use the linear function in theoretical calculations.

In addition to this, we may assert that out of all the coefficients M_i only M_1 (and, of course, M_0) is a well-defined molecular parameter, which along with r_e , ω_e , $\omega_e x_e$ etc. characterises the molecular properties near the equilibrium position. To check the validity of this statement, look at table 3 where sets of the coefficients M_i are gathered for various molecules and, in particular, six sets for HF and DF evaluated in different ways, namely from the absorption and emission spectra, with use of the Morse and RKR potentials and of a different number of terms in the $d(q)$ expansion. It is obvious that in the case of HF and DF, the first coefficient M_1 keeps constant with a high accuracy: its variations within the first six

lines of table 3 are less than 1%. Further, it should be noted that regular variations in the molecular constants take place along the row of similar compounds HF, HCl, HBr and HI: r_e increases monotonously while ω_e and $\omega_e x_e$ decrease. As is seen from table 3, M_1 also varies in a regular manner: it has the largest value for HF and then decreases along this row, even changing its sign for HI. Nothing like is observed for other parameters M_i , which vary randomly not only in going from one molecule to another, but also for a given molecule depending on the way of data processing and on the type of the data used. That is why we cannot agree with Benesch's opinion [113] that "the constants of the electric dipole moment function are at least as "spectroscopic" as those of the potential function". The above considerations show that the parameters M_i at $i \geq 2$ are characteristic of the way of approximating the dipole moment function rather than of the molecular properties*.

The Ferguson and Parkinson's conclusion is supported by our results regarding the normal band intensities in the overtone spectra. According to (39), the relative higher overtone oscillator strengths depend only on the potential function. The fact that the Meredith and Smith's results [14] were similar for two functions $\mathcal{E}(q)$ is explained as being due to close proximity of the Morse and RKR potentials within the range of $q < 0$ and $\mathcal{E}(q) < D$. Actually, significant contribution to the transition probability is provided by the ranges more distant from the equilibrium position where $\mathcal{E}(q) > D$ (see § 2.4) and these potentials are strongly different from one another and from the true potential, which we approximated there by the exponential function (43). Moreover, Meredith and Smith intentionally chose different $d(q)$ (see table 3) to diminish as much as possible discrepancies between the calculated and measured values of the matrix elements; clearly, the influence of the potential would be more distinguishable when using the same functions $d(q)$.

The situation is, however quite different when anomalous bands emerge. The Meredith-Smith's result that the matrix elements for the quadratic and cubic dipole moment functions were much different has been explained in § 2.6 in terms of an anomaly caused by vanishing the preexponential factor in the matrix element (38), which has been neglected in deriving equation (39). The anomaly occurs at one or two adjacent bands only, not imposing any disturbance on the intensity distribution among the other (normal) bands, which again is independent of the dipole moment function. Nevertheless, the anomalous band intensities are extremely sensitive to the form of $d(q)$ so that one can, in principle, use them to reconstruct this function. More detailed study of such a possibility was beyond the scope of the present work.

The normal intensity distribution of the higher overtone bands was derived in § 2.3 under the assumption that the repulsive branch of the potential could be described by a simple expression (43). Such a represen-

* Table 3 does not include the Burberry and Albrecht's data [40] for the benzene local CH vibrations since the coefficient M_1 strongly varies depending on the choice of the potential (by about 30%) and on replacing H by D (by a factor of 1.6).

tation of the repulsive potential is well-known in the theory of atomic collisions and the values of the parameter 2β were experimentally determined for a lot of atomic pairs each involving at least one rare gas atom [122]. For molecules, such a parameter appears to be introduced here for the first time (by definition (43), β is here twice as low as compared to [122]).

All the consequences of the theory deduced in § 2.3, 2.4, 2.6 and at the beginning of § 3 are confirmed both numerical calculations (see § 2.5) and the experiment. In § 3, the experimental data for all the diatomic systems that could be found in literature were examined. The analysis showed that in all the cases considered with no one exception the intensity distribution in the absorption spectra obeyed the normal law (45) (or (74) on the common logarithm scale) and those in the emission spectra obeyed the law (49), the intensities of only a few (one or two in the whole spectrum) absorption bands of diatomic molecules being anomalously low.

The normal intensity distribution law is represented by a straight line on the plot of the intensity logarithm as a function of square root of the upper level energy referred to the potential minimum and normalized to a harmonic frequency quantum. According to (46), the slope of this line is expressed in terms of the usual molecular and fundamental constants and of only one unknown parameter β . The experimental distributions fitting well to this law, the parameter β was determined for all the systems studied. Its values are given in table 6 in parallel to the corresponding ones of the Morse range parameter α characteristic of the potential behavior near the equilibrium. As well included there are the values of the slope a of the straight line describing the normal intensity distribution on the common logarithm scale (see definition (74)).

Unfortunately, we are not aware of any theoretical or experimental data to be compared with the β values obtained in the present work. On this reason, the parameter β was defined in (43) in a manner enabling a comparison with the corresponding parameter of the Morse potential, which behaves like $\mathcal{G}(q) = D \exp(-2\alpha q)$ at $q \rightarrow -\infty$. Such a comparison given in table 6 shows that $\beta > \alpha$ holds for all the systems listed, i. e. the true potential increases faster than the Morse one.

Consider the results for the CH local vibrations in polyatomic molecules. Burberry et al. [41, 55, 56] have shown that for the large polyatomic molecules with a great number of the CH bonds, the absorption band intensities are essentially similar among different molecules, being nearly independent of molecular structure and of the location of the CH bond. Hence the parameter β is the same for all such bonds, being equal to 3.81 \AA^{-1} . It was found out here that β had approximately the same value, 3.76 \AA^{-1} , for relatively small molecules CH_2Cl_2 and CH_2Br_2 (Fang and Swofford [58] have reported the relative intensities only, so it is not known whether the absolute intensities of the CH absorption bands in these molecules fit to the averaged data for large polyatomic molecules [41, 55]). On the other hand, for the CHCl_3 and CHBr_3 molecules β has an appreciably lower value 3.10 \AA^{-1} . This suggests that the haloid substituents affect the CH bond potential if the halogenation leaves only one CH bond unchanged;

even two CH bonds unsubstituted in CH_2X_2 are sufficient for them to become insensitive to their surroundings. Thus it is expected that for the CH_3X compounds β should be the same as for the large polyatomic molecules. It is interesting that the sort of the substituent ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br) does not affect the relative band intensities [58] and, consequently, the β value.

Now look at the β variations among the similar compounds HF, HCl, HBr and HI. The Morse range parameter is steadily decreasing along this row and so do the slope of the straight line representing the normal intensity distribution. However, β falls from HF to HCl and then increases monotonously. This appears to be connected with a sharp fall in the harmonic frequency ω_e (by about 1000 cm^{-1}) from HF to HCl, which is then slowly decreasing by about 300 cm^{-1} from HCl to HBr and from HBr to HI. According to (80), the sharp decrease in ω_e from HF to HCl results in decreasing β in spite of the fact that the slope a is decreasing as well.

In table 6, CO is the only molecule with no light atom H. According to (54), a larger reduced molecular mass results in a larger slope, i. e. the higher overtone band intensities will be greatly lowered. So the CO slope is twice as high as the CH one. However, when the mass change is small, as is the case for deuterium substituted diatomics CD and DF, the slope change is expected to be very slight (see (77)). The experiment qualitatively supports this prediction but on unknown reasons the scatter of the experimental points becomes greatly enhanced after the deuterium substitution, which does not permit a quantitative comparison of the theory with experiment to be made.

The present work shows that isolated bands with appreciably lowered intensities can emerge in the normal intensity distributions of the overtone absorption. Recall that the normal distribution arises from the exponential factor of the dipole moment matrix element whereas the anomalies occur for the transitions where the factor ρ is close to zero. This phenomenon was first discovered by Meredith and Smith [14] who calculated the HF $n \leftarrow 0$ absorption band intensities at $n \leq 10$ and obtained that the $n=6$ band intensity was anomalously low for a cubic dipole moment function, this effect having been absent for a quadratic function. However, these authors gave an incorrect explanation to this result having concluded that the intensity distribution in the whole spectrum was dependent on the form of $d(q)$. In fact, as was shown here, the intensity distribution on the whole is independent of the form of $d(q)$ but whether the preexponential factor vanishes, and where exactly, i. e. whether there are anomalies in the spectrum, strongly depends on $d(q)$. It was said above that the coefficients of the $d(q)$ expansion in powers of the displacement q are not good molecular parameters. But nevertheless they provide a rough representation for $d(q)$ in a wide range of nuclear displacements. These coefficients collected in table 3 were used here for calculating the factors ρ and it was found out that the Meredith—Smith anomalies should be present in the HCl, HBr, HI and CO absorption spectra. The analysis of the experimental data for the first three molecules revealed the occurrence of the anomalies just at the levels predicted in table 4. The CO anomaly is predicted at level $n=5$. An attempt to calculate the CO anomalous band intensities using ρ from

table 4 was not successful because ρ was quite sensitive to the explicit form of $d(q)$ near the energy where it goes across zero. But this implies that $d(q)$ could be reconstructed with much higher precision using the intensities of only the anomalous bands rather than those of all the bands in the spectrum.

It is worthwhile to note that the anomaly position steadily shifts to lower levels n in going from HF to HI. Note also that the anomaly positions only weakly depend on the $d(q)$ representation chosen provided that the expansion in powers of q contains the powers not less than the third. For example, the ρ values calculated for HF with three sets of the coefficients M_i from lines 3 to 5 of table 3 give the positions of two anomalous bands within $n=4$ to 7, while $n=3, 4$ is predicted for DF. However, we were not able to reveal this anomaly in the HF and DF overtone emission spectra since the HF energy differences between the initial and final states seemed to be too low and the DF point scatter was too high. It should be taken into account that if an anomaly in the absorption spectrum is predicted at level n_a then the corresponding anomaly in the emission spectrum will be at such $n_e \rightarrow m_e$ transitions that

$$\varepsilon_{n_e} - \varepsilon_{m_e} = \varepsilon_{n_a} - \varepsilon_0.$$

In other words, the condition $n_e - m_e \geq n_a$ must be fulfilled because of reducing the level separations with an increase in n and m .

A relatively large experimental point scatter in the HF and OH emission spectra (see figures 5 and 7) and differences in the slopes of the straight lines in figures 5 and 6 appear to result from substituting the exponential function (43) for the potential in the whole energy range, which could be a too rough approximation. Actually, it is valid only in an asymptotic limit of large negative displacements whereas the range of small displacements also provides a contribution to the integral S_{mn} in equation (36). In general one could relax the approximation (43) and make an attempt to reconstruct the true potential $\mathcal{G}(q)$ exactly. To this end, one could take the RKR potential (e. g. the HF one from [14]) and extend it to large negative displacements with use of a smooth "switching" function in such a way that the potential tended to the asymptotic limit (43) with β from table 6. The parameters of the switching function could be chosen such that to fit the calculated relative intensities to the experimental ones. Equations (36)–(38) with $q_0 = -\infty$ should be used for calculating the intensities for a given potential. Considering that the HF anomaly is not expected to occur at $n-m < 6$, the dipole moment should be replaced by a linear function as was recommended by Ferguson and Parkinson [100]. Then the factor ρ in (38) is merely a constant and does not affect the relative intensities. Such a study was, however, beyond the scope of the present work.

After the paper had been completed, data on the SiH local mode overtone absorption in SiH₄ were published [132]. They are on a straight line with $a = 5.20 \pm 0.18$ giving $\beta = (2.98 \pm 0.10) \text{ \AA}^{-1}$.

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APPENDIX

The functional ρ for power functions

For the power functions $V(x) = x^n$ the functional (32) can be expressed through the values of the functions

$$A_n(t) \equiv y \int_0^\infty (\ln z)^n z^{t-1} e^{-yz} dz \quad (\text{A1})$$

at $t=1$. Changing the integration variable in the integral (32) as $z \rightarrow yz$ and using the notation $a_n = A_n(1)$ we get

$$\rho[1, y] = 0, \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$\rho[x, y] = 1, \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$\rho[x^2, y] = 2a_1, \quad (\text{A4})$$

$$\rho[x^3, y] = 3a_2 - \pi^2, \quad (\text{A5})$$

$$\rho[x^4, y] = 4a_3 - 4\pi^2 a_1, \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$\rho[x^5, y] = 5a_4 - 10\pi^2 a_2 + \pi^4, \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$\rho[x^6, y] = 6a_5 - 20\pi^2 a_3 + 6\pi^4 a_1. \quad (\text{A8})$$

At $n=0, 1$ the integrals (A1) are

$$A_0(t) = y^{1-t} \Gamma(t), \quad (\text{A9})$$

$$A_1(t) = \frac{d}{dt} A_0(t) = -A_0(t) [\ln y - \psi(t)], \quad (\text{A10})$$

where $\Gamma(t)$ is the Gamma-function and $\psi(t) = d \ln \Gamma(t) / dt$. At $n > 1$ they can be found from the relation

$$A_{n+1}(t) = \frac{d^n}{dt^n} A_1(t). \quad (\text{A11})$$

Taking the n -th derivative of equation (A10) and letting

$$\tau = \ln y - \psi(1), \quad (\text{A12})$$

we obtain the following recurrence relation for the coefficients a_n at $n \geq 1$:

$$a_{n+1} = -\tau a_n + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!} \psi^{(k)}(1) a_{n-k}, \quad (\text{A13})$$

where $\psi^{(k)}(1)$ is the k -th derivative of the ψ -function at $t=1$ and

$$a_0 = 1, \quad a_1 = -\tau, \quad a_2 = \tau^2 + \psi^{(1)}(1) \quad (\text{A14})$$

and so on. Numerical values of the ψ -function and its derivatives at $t=1$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(1) &= -0.577216, \\ \psi^{(1)}(1) &= 1.644934, \\ \psi^{(2)}(1) &= -2.404113, \\ \psi^{(3)}(1) &= 6.493939, \\ \psi^{(4)}(1) &= -24.886266. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A15})$$

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